

University of
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UNIVERSITY OF
DELAWARE

TURNEYES 892951

RESEARCHER ANNEMARIE WALTER
OUTGOING SUPERVISOR DAVID REDLAWSK
INCOMING SUPERVISOR CEES VAN DER EIJK

REPORT 1

STUDY 1: MORAL AND
PARTISAN IDENTITY

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Introduction

Moral transgressions, violations of widely held moral principles, are often precursors to political scandals which are “actions or events involving certain kinds of transgressions which become known to others and are sufficiently serious to elicit a public response” (Thompson, 2000:13). While a great deal of research exists on political scandals, there is less on the moral transgressions that lead to them. Moral transgressions by politicians differ as do the intensities of voters’ responses. These varied responses may provide some understanding of why politicians involved in scandals are not consistently punished by the electorate (Fernández-Vázquez, Barberá, & Rivero, 2016).

Scholars trying to explain the puzzle of the heterogeneity in voters’ responses to transgressions have paid only limited attention to the role of social identity (notable exceptions are Solaz, De Vries & De Geus, 2019; and Solomon, Hackathorn, Crittendon, 2019), instead focusing primarily on voters’ partisanship (Anduiza et al., 2013; Bhatti et al., 2013; Blais et al., 2010; Fischle, 2000, Walter & Redlawsk, 2019, 2021; Redlawsk & Walter, 2024; Solomon, Hackathorn, Crittendon, 2019), and overlooking the roles of other identities.¹ One understudied identity that should condition voters’ responses to moral transgressions is moral identity, defined by Aquino and Reed (2002) as the extent to which people’s self-concept is organized around their moral beliefs. In this context, people’s moral identity is core to their moral judgments and behavior (Hertz & Kattenauer, 2016) and

¹ Moreover, studies that examine partisanship as a basis of voter response to scandal rarely measure partisanship as an identity (Huddy, et al. 2001), but simply as a group membership. A partisan identity measure such as the one developed by Banker, Huddy & Rosema (2017) assesses to what extent partisanship is important to one’s self concept and uses statements such as ‘When people criticize this party, it feels like a personal insult’ and ‘When I meet someone who supports this party, I feel connected with this person’. This is quite different from simply asking people if they think of themselves as a member of a particular party.

should not be ignored when trying to understand voters' evaluations of politicians' moral transgressions.

This study examines how voters' heterogeneous responses to politicians' moral violations depend on multiple identities. While there are many identities that could come into play, we focus here on partisan and moral identities, the internalization of these identities, and the partisanship of the involved politician. We conduct studies in both the United States and England, two English speaking established Western democracies with both similarities and differences in their political systems (Strohmeier, 2015).² We administered a 6 x 3 between-subjects vignette study where participants viewed a vignette describing a politician as violating one of five moral principles drawn from Moral Foundations Theory (Graham, et al. 2011), i.e. Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority, or Sanctity, or a non-moral Social Norm violation, used as a control. In addition to manipulating the violated moral principle, the study also varied the partisanship of the actor (U.S.: Republican/Democrat/nonpartisan; England: Conservative/Labour/nonpartisan). In both countries, a random sample of about 3,000 respondents was surveyed. From these data, we focus here on respondents reporting a partisan social identity as defined by Bankert, Huddy and Rosema (2017), and who were shown one of the five moral violation vignettes. This removes respondents who are non-leaning independents and respondents exposed to a social norm violation, as well as those with missing data on dependent or independent variables. This leaves 1,719 U.S. cases and 1,396 cases for England for analysis.

We find that in both countries partisan identity and moral identity both affect voters'

² We conduct the experiment in England instead of the United Kingdom, as the different countries that make up the UK have different party systems, which would add unnecessary complication to the data collection. We chose England to extend research that has traditionally focused only on the United States to facilitate comparisons between western, English-speaking democracies.

evaluations of politicians involved in moral violations, validating our argument that multiple identities likely play roles in such evaluations. People tend to evaluate ingroup politicians violating moral values more favorably than outgroup politicians. In the U.S., voters with Republican partisan identities exhibit a stronger ingroup bias than Democrats, although a similar partisan identity effect is not present in England. Voters in both countries show increasing ingroup bias as the internalization of partisan identity increases. In addition to partisan identity effects, we find that the more central people's moral identity is to their self-concept, the more unlikeable they consider both in- and outgroup politicians who violate moral principles. However, in the U.S., but not England, partisan ingroup bias remains regardless the extent to which moral identity is important to people's self-concept. Our results argue that to solve the puzzle of heterogeneous voter responses to politicians' immoral behavior, we need to take voters' multiple identities into account, specifically moral identities in addition to partisan identities.

Beyond extending our understanding of voter responses to politicians' moral violations, this study contributes to the literature on ingroup bias in evaluations of group members and on how holding multiple social identities affects intergroup attitudes. More specifically, it extends work connecting heterogeneous voters' responses to social identity theory (Solaz, De Vries & De Geus, 2019; Solomon, Hackathorn, Crittendon, 2019) with a specific focus on partisan and moral identities.

Voters' Multiple Identities

Social identity is a subjective sense of belonging to a group, and is an important part of a person's self-concept (Tajfel, 1981). People can, and likely do, have multiple social identities due to beliefs, such as religious and moral beliefs, and their involvement in

activities, such as professional and political groups. Some of these identities are acquired through inheritance, life experiences, or accomplishments. These identities differ in internalization, i.e. the extent that they are central to people's self-concept, as well as in their stability or changeability, and the status they provide a person (Kulich et al., 2017). Not all people's identities are accessible in their working self-concept at the same time; identities can be (de)activated by situational factors. For example, when attending religious services, one's religious identity is likely to be in the forefront, compared to other identities that may matter in different circumstances. The more internalized identities are, the more easily they are activated (Aquino et al. 2009). Identities that are central to a person's self-concept and activated affect how information is interpreted, judgments made, and behaviors that result.

People engage (un)consciously in creating and maintaining a positive social identity, which can include biased information processing, intergroup bias in perceptions, and ingroup favoritism and outgroup derogation of behaviors (Huddy & Bankert 2017; Hewstone, Rubin, Willis, 2002). However, outgroup derogation is not a necessary extension of ingroup favoritism (Hewstone, Rubin, Willis, 2002). Intergroup bias tends to go beyond ingroup favoritism when strong emotions, such as disgust, fear, and anger, are associated with the outgroup, elicited when outgroups violate ingroup norms (Brewer 2001). Ingroup bias may be moderated by factors such as identification strength, group size, status, power, personality traits, and individual difference variables (Hewstone, Rubin, Willis 2002).

Social groups have their own moral principles, i.e. values that help members distinguish between "right" and "wrong" and define behavioral expectations of group members. Consequently, social groups differ in what they consider moral or immoral behavior (Ellemers, 2018). Group members tend to obey these moral principles as they gain

respect for doing so and avoid sanctions for violating them. A group member violating the group's moral principles can be considered a potential threat to positive group image and might lead to other group members distancing from and/or rejecting the transgressor (Van der Lee et al, 2017). People's own morality, as well as judgements about other people's morality, is influenced by their social identity, as judgments of ingroup members' morality are motivated by concerns of how their behavior affects the group identity and thus reflects upon people's self-concept. Judgments of outgroup members' morality are motivated by concerns of group safety (Ellemers, 2018).

When people identify with a social group, the group's failures and victories become personal (Smith & Mackie, 2016). People are less tolerant of an immoral than an incompetent group member, as the first is perceived to be a larger threat to the positive group image than the latter (Van der Lee et al, 2017)

Recently, scholars have been documenting the alignment of social identity with political preferences in the U.S. and the resulting reinforcement of partisan polarization (Mason & Wronski, 2018). Partisanship has become internalized, at least for strong partisans, becoming another social identity that conditions responses to political events, and not just a group membership. Political events are often connected to moral principles. Moral identity can also be activated as part of one's social identity when politics and morality intersect (Aquino & Reed, 2002). Given this, we focus here on these two key social identities - moral identity and partisan identity - which can be activated by political events and condition how voters respond to politicians.

Partisan and Moral Identities

Studies examining how voters' partisan identities affect responses to politicians'

immoral behavior tend to focus on partisanship as a group affiliation (e.g. Blais et al. 2010; Walter & Redlawsk 2019, 2021; Redlawsk & Walter, 2024) rather than as a social identity³ Most studies find that politicians engaging in immoral behavior who are members of a voter's own party are more positively evaluated than out-party politicians doing the same thing (Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; Solomon, Hackathorn, Crittendon, 2019) and that the strength of this ingroup bias is dependent on the strength of the voter's partisan affiliation (Walter & Redlawsk, 2021; Craig Cossette, 2020).

Here we redirect this work by following Huddy and Bankert (2017) in conceptualizing and measuring partisan identity as a *social* identity with varying levels of centrality. We examine partisan effects based on the centrality of partisan identity, rather than just the feeling of belonging measured by group affiliation. Given the earlier findings on the role of partisanship as a group membership, we anticipate that recasting and measuring partisan strength as a social identity will better clarify the role it plays in responding to moral transgressions by politicians.

At the same time, other identities surely play roles as well. An identity that is surprisingly overlooked in studies attempting to explain voters' heterogeneous responses to politicians' moral transgressions is moral identity, defined as a self-conception organized around a set of specific moral traits (Aquino & Reed, 2002). Moral identity is a social identity that may be activated as a part of a person's social self-schema. Moral identity may have a social referent in the form of a real membership group, an abstract ideal, an (un)known individual, or a social construction (Aquino & Reed, 2002). While there has been limited

³ Typically, these studies use questions that focus on membership, rather than identity, where partisan strength is operationalized as the extent to which the respondent calls themselves a strong or weak partisan, or if initially non-partisan, says they "lean" toward a particular party. See operationalization section for more details on measuring partisan identity as a social identity.

attention in political science to moral identity in the context of political scandal and moral violations, in psychology the concept of moral identity is commonly used to explain people's moral judgment and behavior. A meta-analysis by Hertz and Krettenauer (2016) of 111 studies finds that moral identity significantly predicts moral behavior. We argue that moral identity should be an important motivator of responses to politicians who violate moral principles.

People differ in the extent that being a moral person is part of their overall self-definition (Hardy & Carlo, 2011). For people for whom it is very central to their self-concept relative to other identities, moral identity tends to be relatively stable over time. However, like any other social identity, people's moral identity can be more or less salient in different contexts. People who hold a strong moral identity are more likely to interpret situations in a moral manner and act accordingly (Hertz & Krettenauer, 2016), despite situational influences, as they strive for consistency between their moral self and their actions (Aquino et al., 2009; Aquino & Reed, 2002). Thus, moral identity may play an important role in voters' responses to moral transgressors in the political domain.

Hypotheses

We propose a series of hypotheses about how both partisan and moral identities should influence responses to politicians who violate moral principles. We use Moral Foundations Theory (MFT) to provide a set of potential moral violations with which to test our expectations (Graham et al., 2011). MFT categorizes moral principles into five foundations: Care; Fairness; Loyalty; Authority; and Sanctity (Haidt & Graham, 2007).⁴ The

⁴ We acknowledge that MFT's validity is contested, including the question of how many moral foundations there are (e.g. Iurino & Saucier, 2020) and the extent to which the "foundations" are causal first principles (Hatemi, Crabtree, & Smith, 2019; Ciuk, 2018; Smith et al., 2017). MFT claims to present an universal theory of

moral foundation Care refers to the dislike for the suffering of others. Fairness focuses on the commitment to fairness and justice. Loyalty is seen as a commitment to one's own group. The moral foundation Authority refers to respect for authority and tradition, and Sanctity refers to concerns with purity and contamination.

Our first set of hypotheses examines the extent to which the most politically relevant social identity – partisan identity – conditions responses to moral violations by politicians. Even as we shift our measurement of partisan identity strength to the Huddy and Bankert (2016) social identity approach, we expect earlier findings on partisanship to hold. Consequently, we formulate the following hypotheses:

Partisan Ingroup Bias Hypothesis (H1): People evaluate politicians engaged in moral violations who belong to their party (ingroup) more positively than politicians who do not (outgroup).

Partisan Identity Centrality (H2): The more central people's partisan social identity, the greater the ingroup bias when evaluating politicians involved in moral violations.

While partisan identity is likely crucial to voters' responses to partisan politicians, given that we are studying moral transgressions, we also need to turn to voters' moral identities to better understand how they respond as moral identity guides moral behavior (Aquino & Reed, 2002; Hertz & Kattenauer, 2016). Much like the centrality of partisan

moral reasoning and thus to be applicable beyond any specific national context, yet findings on the applicability of MFT in the English political context are mixed (Walter, 2020; Harper & Rhodes, 2021). Nonetheless, we do not plan to wade into that controversy here. Our purpose in using MFT is to identify a set of potential moral principles that might relate to politics, no matter the causal direction between the moral foundations and political ideology. MFT provides a useful guide for the vignettes we use in which politician violate moral principles. The political scandal literature also finds there are a wide range of moral principles which may be violated. While the literature also distinguishes various types of scandals, 61% of research studies are devoted to sex or corruption scandals (Von Sikorski, 2018).

identity, we expect the centrality of a voter's moral identity to also condition responses to moral transgressions, independently of partisan effects, so that once partisanship is accounted for, we should see little ingroup bias in such responses.

Moral Identity Strength (H3): The more central moral identity, the more likely people will negatively evaluate all politicians involved in moral violations, across both in- and outgroups.

The centrality of moral identity for a person's self-concept affects the relationship between the self and the other (Aquino & Reed, 2003). Several studies find that moral identity mitigates ingroup favoritism and outgroup hostility (Aquino & Reed 2003; Smith et al. 2014), with people more likely to perceive out-group members as also worthy of moral consideration (Smith et al. 2014). This leads to reducing the likelihood of wishing to harm to outgroup members and making people more likely to forgive and help them (Aquino & Reed, 2003; Winterich, Mittal, Ross. Jr., 2009). So while H3 suggests that both in- and outgroup violators will be more negatively evaluated, the gap between in- and outgroup politician evaluations should also be reduced as moral identity strength increases. Thus, we propose H4:

Moral Identity Ingroup Bias Attenuation (H4): The more central people's moral identity, the more negatively they will evaluate ingroup politicians involved in moral transgressions, reducing ingroup bias.

Data Collection and Method of Analysis

To examine how multiple identities affect responses to politicians' moral violations we conducted a between-subjects vignette study in a 6 (5 moral violations and 1 social norm violation) x 3 (levels of partisanship) design embedded in a survey administered to approximately 3,000 respondents in each of two countries, the United States and England. Both are English speaking Western democracies with two and two-and-a-half party systems (Strohmeier, 2015) respectively. We examine two countries to assess the generalizability of our argument across democracies and to extend work that has mostly focused on the United States in the past. Each respondent was randomly assigned one short vignette describing a fictional, but realistic sounding, scenario in which a politician violated a moral principle or social norm. We manipulated the violated moral principle drawing inspiration from the MFT framework (Graham et al. 2011), while adding a social norm violation as a non-moral baseline. In addition, we varied the partisanship of the politician (US: Republican, Democrat, no party; England: Labour, Conservative, no party) in the vignette.

Vignette Pre-testing

The six scenarios listed in Table 1 were drawn from a pre-test of 30 vignettes using an Amazon Mechanical Turk heterogeneous sample of U.S. respondents and a heterogeneous Prolific sample of English respondents. Full details of the pre-tests of 30 possible vignettes and the selection process for the ones used in this study are included in Appendix 4 of the Supplementary Materials. Vignettes were initially developed by modifying some of Clifford, et al.'s (2015) standardized vignettes to fit a political context, following Walter and Redlawsk (2019). Vignettes used in this study were selected as the best representation of each moral principle and social norm based on pre-test responses.

Selected vignettes were best perceived by pre-test respondents as being both understandable and realistic. Most importantly, we also asked pre-test respondents to categorize the moral violation using MFT labels; the ones selected were most likely to be seen as a case of the particular moral violation we intended. The MTurk and Prolific samples were used only to pre-test the vignettes and not for the study we report here.

Table 1: Vignettes Used in Survey Embedded Experiment

Transgression	Moral principle violated	Vignette(non-partisan)
Moral	Care	You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems
Moral	Fairness	You see a politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs
Moral	Loyalty	You see a politician town say the neighbo[u]ring town is better
Moral	Authority	You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police/Chief Constable at a disaster
Moral	Sanctity	You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager
Social norm		You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol/Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag

Note: The table only displays the nonpartisan vignettes of the survey embedded experiment, for partisan vignettes insert Republican/Democrat or Labour/Conservative in front of the word politician. See Appendix 3 in the Supplementary Materials for full details.

Study Samples and design

Respondents for the two online studies reported here were drawn from Dynata samples, one in England and the other in the United States. The U.S. sample was designed to closely match the American adult population on age, gender, race/ethnicity, income, and region of residence. The England sample was designed to closely match the English adult population on age and gender. Sample characteristics are described in Tables A2.3 and A2.4 in Appendix 2 of the Supplementary Materials. The US data were collected between October 2, 2020 and November 3, 2020, in the context of the U.S. presidential election. The England data were collected between November 16 and November 30, 2020.

At the beginning of the survey, respondents were asked basic demographics, following which each viewed a single randomly selected vignette, eliminating any spillover effects from viewing multiple violations (see Supplementary Materials Tables A2.5 and A2.6 for the randomization checks). Following the vignette, respondents were asked to evaluate the politician described in the vignette and rate his/her likeability on a 7-point scale running from 1 (Unlikeable) to 7 (Likeable). Given that the information provided to respondents was about the violation of a moral or social norm, the distribution of the variable is unsurprisingly skewed towards the left side of the scale (Figures A1.1 to A 1.4 in the Supplementary Materials). Following evaluations of the politician's action, respondents then completed a series of questions meant to tap partisan and moral social identities. These items were used to create the identity and centrality scales described below. The questionnaire is available in Appendix 5 of the Supplementary Materials.

Initial analyses were carried out on the full datasets (US N=2988 and England N=3011) to test whether exposure to a moral violation results in different evaluations of the likeability of a politician compared to exposure to a social norm violation.⁵ As expected, we find that both U.S. and English voters perceive politicians as less likeable when involved in a moral violation than they do with a social norm violation (Tables A1.5 and A1.7 in the Supplementary Materials.) The marginal effects show that, on average, U.S. respondents exposed to a moral violation were 9.3 percentage points more likely than those exposed to a social norm violation to say that the politician involved as Unlikeable (1 on the scale), and about 3.5 percentage points less likely to say that the politician involved is Likeable (7 on the scale; Supplementary Materials Table A1.6). On average English respondents exposed to a

⁵ In the US data we drop 5 observations and in England we drop 3 observations due to missing data on the dependent variable, Politician Likeability.

moral violation are 33.2 percentage points more likely than respondents exposed to a social norm violation to say that the politician involved is Unlikeable and about 10.5 percentage points less likely to say that the politician involved is Likeable (Supplementary Materials Table A1.8)

Having established that the moral violations are in fact different from the social norm violation, we restrict the remaining analyses to only include participants who viewed the moral violation vignettes which are the focus of this study. In order to identify partisan identity effects, we also drop respondents who did not at least indicate some support for one of the major parties. In the United States that means we restrict analyses to Republicans and Democrats (leaning, weak, or strong). In England, for reasons of comparability to the U.S., we restrict ourselves Labour and Conservative Party identifiers, dropping other party adherents. The resulting sample sizes for the analyses below are 1719 respondents in the US study and 1396 in England.⁶

Operationalization of Covariates

We need to be clear about partisanship, since we operationalize it both as a group affiliation and as a social identity, for different purposes in the analyses. As a group affiliation, respondent reported partisan preference is used to identify the correspondence between the partisanship of the politician in the vignettes and the partisan preference of the respondent, allowing us to categorize ingroup and outgroup politicians. Partisanship as a

⁶ In the U.S. data we drop 501 respondents when eliminating those exposed to the social norm vignettes and we drop another 403 respondents who have no party preference at all and therefore are not relevant to our ingroup and outgroup analyses, along with 361 respondents with missing values on the Partisan Identity Centrality measure. In the English data we drop 508 respondents exposed to the social norm vignette, 283 no party preference, 265 Liberal Democrats, 115 Green, 83 UKIP and 34 other partisans (to maintain focus on Labour and Conservative identifiers), and another 327 respondents due to missing values on the variable Partisan Identity Centrality.

social identity is measured independently and is used to estimate the importance of the centrality of partisan identity in responses to moral violations by politicians.

Partisanship as *group membership* is measured in the U.S. survey using the typical 7-point scale, constructed from a series of questions that first ask whether the respondent is a Democrat, Republican, or Independent, and then ask the strength of the party preference. Independents were asked whether they leaned one way or the other. Partisanship in England is measured on the basis of two questions that first ask whether the respondent generally thinks of her or himself as Labour, Conservative, Liberal Democrat or what? Following this, strength of preference is recorded.

Shared Partisanship links the partisanship of the politician and the respondent, where the value 1 indicates that the respondent shares partisanship with the politician portrayed in the vignette and the value 0 indicates that the respondent and politician do not.

Partisan Identity Centrality uses the 4-item Partisan Identity Scale developed by Bankert, Huddy and Rosema (2017), which measures partisan identity internalization and sense of belonging, as an expressive approach to partisanship. The items are worded for a specific party based on the respondent's answer to the traditional partisanship question (Huddy et al. 2015), and thus are not asked of non-leaning independents. The items constitute a strong uni-dimensional additive scale, scored from 4 to 16, with a Homogeneity Coefficient of .616 for the US data and .619 for the England data, see Table A2.11 and Table A2.12 in the supplementary materials. For our analyses, we divided the sample into three partisan centrality groups: respondents with scores of 9 and lower show low partisan centrality;

respondents with scores of 10 to 12 show moderate centrality; and respondents with scores of 13 and higher are high centrality partisans. This results in a distribution of partisan identity centrality for the US data of 30.4% low, 44.2% moderate, and 25.4% high. The distribution of partisan identity centrality for England is 52.0% low, 36.9% moderate, and 11.1% high.

Moral Identity is measured using Aquino and Reed's (2002) 10-item Self-Importance of Moral Identity Scale, which assesses the centrality of moral identity as reflected in a series of traits associated with a moral person. This is the most widely used explicit measure of moral identity (Hertz & Kattenauer, 2016) and assumes that although the content of people's moral identities varies, there is a common set of traits central to most individuals' moral self-concept. After being told to visualize a person who holds this set of moral traits, respondents are asked to rate 10 statements about themselves on a 5-point scale (1=Strongly disagree, 5=Strongly agree). The result is the identification of two subscales, Internalization and Symbolization. Internalization measures the degree to which moral traits are central to one's self-concept and Symbolization measures the extent to which moral traits are reflected in behavior visible to others (Aquino & Reed, 2002). Mokken scale analysis (Mokken, 1971) of our data shows that the five ordinal Internalization items constitute a strong uni-dimensional scale with a Homogeneity coefficient of .500 for the US and .468 for England; see Tables A2.7 and A2.8 in the Supplementary Materials. The five ordinal symbolization items constitute a medium-strong uni-dimensional scale with a Homogeneity coefficient of .468 for the US data and .476 for the England data; see Tables

A2.9 and A2.10 in the Supplementary Materials.⁷ Both composite additive scales run from 5 to 25. For our analyses we recode both scales into 3 groups: low (5-15), moderate (16-20) and high moral identity (21-25).⁸

Results

For ease of interpretation we have chosen to present figures derived from our models in the following section; the ordered probit models on which these are based are presented in Appendix 1 of the Supplementary Materials. In all models, the dependent variable is politician likeability. We combine all five moral violation types in the analyses, so we are examining what happens when any of these specific moral violations is seen to occur, without differentiating the moral principles implicated in the vignettes. All models control for respondents' age, gender, education level, and race. We organize the following analyses by country, first examining our results from the sample of U.S. respondents and then turning to the England results. Following this, we discuss the findings and their implications.

The United States

Moral Violations and Partisanship

We turn to our initial hypotheses on shared partisanship and partisan identity centrality effects on evaluations of politicians violating moral principles. We find a

⁷ We find small but statistically significant partisan differences in the internalization of moral identity in the U.S., but not the UK. Republicans (19.94) score slightly lower than Democrats (20.43) on moral identity internalization.

⁸For Internalization, the grouping results in 17.8% low, 20.8% moderate, and 51.4% high in the U.S. data and 16.8% low, 35.3% moderate, and 47.9% high in the England data. For Symbolization, the distribution is 42.5% low, 41.1% moderate, and 16.3% high in the U.S. and 37.6% low, 51.4% moderate and 11.0% high in England.

statistically and substantively significant effect for shared partisanship on politician evaluation (See Table A1.9 in the Supplementary Materials). As anticipated, U. S. respondents give same party politicians significantly extra leeway to violate moral principles, as is evident from Figure 1, displaying the predicted probabilities for each level of the dependent variable by ingroup and outgroup violator. Recall that likeability is scaled from 1 (unlikeable) to 7 (likeable). Looking first at Republican voters, we see that reading about a Republican politician violating a moral principle results in a significantly lower likelihood of rating the politician as unlikeable (1) versus reading about a Democratic politician's violation (36.2% versus 45.1%, $t=3.52$, $p<.001$). At the same time, the likelihood of rating the in-party violator at 7 (likeable) on the scale is 10.7% versus 7.0% for a Democrat ($t=-2.81$, $p<.01$). It is very clear that Republican voters provide a margin of acceptability to moral violations for their own politicians far greater than they do for the other side.

Democratic voters are more likely to give a lower rating to a co-partisan politician than Republicans are to theirs. However, like Republicans, Democrats give their own politician significantly more leeway than they do the other party. Among Democrats, the predicted probability of a "1" rating is 46.3% for an own-party politician, compared to 55.5% for the out-party ($t=3.70$, $p<.001$). Paralleling this, the likelihood of the most positive rating (7) for a Democrat by Democratic voters is 6.7% versus 4.2% for a Republican politician ($t=-2.78$, $p<.01$). H1, suggesting ingroup partisan bias is support in the American data.

Partisan Identity Centrality

We next examine H2, which considers the effect of partisan identity centrality - defined and measured as a social identity - on intergroup bias when evaluating politicians

Figure 1: Predicted Levels of Candidate Likeability by Shared Partisan Identity (US)

involved in moral transgressions. Supplementary Materials Table A1.11 shows the full model for this analysis. Figure 2 displays the net difference in predicted probabilities for the in- versus outgroup politician for each level of likeability for the U.S. sample, with a separate figure for each level of partisan identity centrality. Most notably, there are no significant differences in evaluations between in- and outgroup politicians for low identity centrality partisans. Those for whom partisan identity is not an important social identity do not differentiate between their own party and the other party politician.

Figure 2: Predicted Probability Candidate Likeability Levels by Partisan Identity Centrality (US)

However, significant and substantive effects are found for other voters. Moderate centrality U.S. partisans are about 9.2 percentage points more likely to rate a transgressive out-party politician at the lowest level of likeability (1) compared to an in-party politician (t=

2.80, $p < .01$). They are also about 3 points more likely to rate their co-partisan politician at the highest level (7) compared to the other party ($t = -2.23$, $p < .05$). Voters with highly central partisan social identities display even greater ingroup bias, with a nearly 19 percentage point greater likelihood of rating the outparty politician at 1, compared to the inparty ($t = 4.71$, $p < .001$). They are also just under 9 points more likely to rate their co-partisan politician at 7, compared to the other side ($t = -3.74$, $p < .001$). Clearly, within the U.S. sample, the centrality of partisan social identity is strongly related to increased inparty bias as anticipated, supporting H2.

Moral Identity Centrality

Having examined the roles of shared partisanship and partisan identity centrality, we turn to moral identity centrality. Hypothesis 3 suggests that as moral identity becomes more central to one's self, evaluations of a politician violating moral principles should become more negative. As we have noted, the measurement of moral identity includes two subscales: Symbolization and Internalization (Aquino and Reed 2003). We expect that increasing Internalization drives negative evaluations of moral transgressors, since internalization is related to the extent to which one's moral identity is a core self-identity. Symbolization is outward facing, related to the extent to which one wants others to believe we hold a strong moral identity, whether we do or not. In that sense it is a behavior, which is not likely to be activated in our vignettes since no one is watching the participant as they answer questions. Thus we do not expect a relationship between Symbolization and transgressor evaluations.

As Figures 3 and 4 show, the Internalization expectation is supported in our data when we combine both in- and outgroup politicians into a single analysis. (See Table A1.17

in the supplementary materials for the full model). Among U.S. respondents, moral identity Internalization has clear effects on transgressing politician evaluations, with increases in Internalization statistically and substantively related to increases in the likelihood of rating a morals-violating politician at the lowest level of likeability (1). Figure 3 shows the effects for the U.S.; the probability of giving the lowest rating is 31.8% for those lowest in moral identity internalization, climbing to 39.4% at moderate internalization, and to 57.4% at high internalization ($T_{\text{Low-Moderate}}=2.64, p<.01; T_{\text{Moderate-High}}=7.80, p<.001$).

Figure 3: Predicted Probabilities of Likeability for levels of Moral Identity Internalization (US)

As we anticipated and is displayed in Figure 4, moral identity Symbolization does not seem to play a role in attitudes towards a politician violating moral principles in the U.S. The differences across levels of Symbolization are small and statistically insignificant ($M_{\text{Low}}=50.0\%; M_{\text{Moderate}}=47.2\%, t=-1.27, n.s.; M_{\text{High}}=42.3\%, T_{\text{Moderate-High}}=-1.70, n.s.$). Moral identity centrality does appear to condition responses to transgressing politicians, in terms of its internalization, but not its outward expression, providing support for H3.

Figure 4: Predicted Probabilities of Likeability for levels of Moral Identity Symbolization (US)

Moral Identity and Ingroup Bias

Given the results on moral identity centrality, we focus on Internalization to test H4: the Moral Identity Ingroup Bias Attenuation hypothesis. The model for this analysis is shown in Table A1.19 in the Supplementary Materials. Figure 5 displays the net differences in likeability between in- and outgroup politicians in our U. S. sample. As with partisan identity, we find no significant effects at the lowest level of moral identity Internalization; whether the transgressing politician is a co-partisan or not makes no significant difference to evaluations, as we would anticipate.

However, unexpectedly, at moderate and high levels of moral identity internalization in the United States, a partisan gap emerges, so that an inparty politician is not penalized as much as the outparty politician for violating moral principles, even as respondents show greater moral identity Internalization. This effect appears even with partisanship and

Figure 5: Predicted Probabilities of Difference in Likeability of In and Outgroup Politicians for levels of Moral Identity Internalization (US)

partisan identity centrality as controls in the model. At moderate moral identity internalization, U.S. respondents are about 8 percentage points less likely to rate an inparty politician at “1” compared to the outparty ($t=2.27, p<.05$) while for those with the highest level of internalization the difference is just over 13 percentage points ($t=4.42, p<.001$). The effects of the strength of moral identity internalization are nearly as large as the partisan effects reported earlier.

In summary, when we examine ingroup bias within Moral Identity Centrality, we find no significant differences in likeability for inparty politicians violating moral principles at the lowest level of Internalization, with some limited effects for moderate Internalization. However, high Moral Identity Internalization Americans show a substantive and significant gap between their negativity toward an outgroup politician compared to the ingroup. At the same time, the data show that the violation of moral principles comes at a significant cost to U.S. politicians, as U.S. participants are far more likely to rate such politicians as most unlikeable, whether inparty or outparty, even as they remain relatively more positive toward their own party.

England

We turn now to examining our England data, to see whether what we find in the United States is unique to the American context or more generalizable. The English party system is similar to the U.S., in that there are have been two major parties, sitting on the center right and center left. England has additional parties, some of which (Liberal Democrats, for example) regularly win seats in Parliament, but for purposes of a clear comparison with the U.S., we limit our focus to Conservatives and Labour supporters.

Moral Violations and Shared Partisanship

We found a strong shared partisanship effect in the United States as we would expect, such that respondents were generally more forgiving of a transgressing co-partisan than of the other party politician. Republicans show more of this effect than Democrats. Examining Figure 6 (based on the model in Table A1.10), we see some evidence for a shared partisanship effect in England, although it is clearly weaker than in the U.S. In addition, unlike the United States, there is virtually no difference between the parties in evaluating their co-partisan. Figure 6 shows that Conservative Party supporters do not differ from Labour supporters in the extent to which they give their own party politician a “1” rating. Both are about 45% likely to give the lowest evaluation to an inparty politician violating moral principles.

There is a small ingroup bias evident for both parties. Conservative voters are more likely to rate a Labour politician violating moral values at “1” than their own party politician ($t=2.16, p<.05$). Labour supporters show almost exactly the same results ($t=2.37, p<.05$). The effect is not as large as in the U.S., but it does exist.

Thus, we find support for H1, Ingroup Partisan Bias, in both countries. However, the differences between parties and thus the extent of the partisan ingroup bias is much less among voters in England compared to the United States.

Partisan Identity Centrality

In the United States we found that partisan identity centrality plays a key role in evaluating transgressing politicians at moderate and high levels of centrality but not for those for whom a partisan identity is not central. Effects are similar in England

Figure 6: Predicted Probability of each Level of Candidate Likeability by Shared Partisan Identity (England)

(Figure 7; model in Table A1.12). At the weakest level of partisan identity centrality, differences between in- and outgroup politicians are again not significant. For moderate identity centrality, English voters are about 11.5 percentage points less likely to rate their own party’s transgressing politician at “1” compared to the other party ($t= 2.81, p<.01$) while high partisan identity centrality voters are nearly 16 points less likely to do so ($t= -2.25, p<.05$).

Figure 7: Predicted Probability Candidate Likeability Levels by Partisan Identity Centrality (England)

While fewer respondents have highly central partisan identities in England compared to the U.S., the results show that the effects of partisan identity centrality hold in a different political context when considering partisanship as a social identity. As partisan identity centrality increases, so does partisan bias. Results in both countries support H2, the Partisan Identity Centrality Hypothesis.

Moral Identity

Moral Identity centrality effects are visible in our American sample, and we find the effects in England (Figure 8; from Table A1.18) are just as strong, with low Moral Identity Internalization respondents 33.6% likely to rate the transgressing politician at “1”, compared to 42.4% for moderate identity and 59.8% for high identity ($T_{Low-Moderate}=2.59, p<.01$; $T_{Moderate-High}=6.43, p<.001$). Across both countries, Internalized moral identity has strong effects on assessments of politicians who violate moral principles.

Figure 8: Predicted Probabilities of Likeability for levels of Moral Identity Internalization (England)

Unlike in the U.S., however, Moral Identity Symbolization also plays a role in England, but only at its highest level, and the direction of the effect is opposite that of Internalization (Figure 9). In England, low and moderate Symbolization respondents are not different, while high Symbolization respondents are different and substantively less likely to give the lowest rating to morals-violating politicians ($M_{\text{Low}}=52.1\%$; $M_{\text{Moderate}}=48.8\%$, $t=-1.28$, *n.s.*; $M_{\text{High}}=38.1\%$, $T_{\text{Moderate-High}}=-2.49$, $p<.01$).

Figure 9: Predicted Probabilities of Likeability for levels of Moral Identity Symbolization (England)

This reversal among our English participants may make some sense when we consider that Symbolization does not have to be sincere. Perhaps those highest in Symbolization are outwardly displaying moral identity that is not especially central to their actual views of morality. In any case, it is clear that Internalized moral identity is an important predictor of politician evaluation in our studies, monotonically and in the expected direction. We find support for Hypothesis 3 in the context of Moral Identity Internalization.

Moral Identity and Ingroup Bias

Finally, we look further to examine whether there is a partisan bias at any level of Moral Identity Internalization in England as we found in the United States. As with the U.S., and as expected, a stronger Internalized moral identity leads to a greater probability of giving a violating politician a highly unlikeable rating (Figure 10, from the model in Table A1.20). But, unlike the U.S., there are no significant differences across centrality of moral identity in how in- and out-party politicians are rated and thus no apparent partisan bias at any level of moral identity internalization in our England data. Americans prefer their own party candidate, even when morally transgressive, over the other party. English respondents at all levels of Moral Identity Internalization rate both in and outparty transgressors as equally disliked.

Across both countries we find no support for H4, which suggested a reduction in ingroup bias as the centrality of moral identity increases. Like partisan identity, moral identity predicts evaluations of politicians who violate moral principles. The effects of moral identity Internalization are strong and consistent across both countries we studied: the greater the Internalization the more likely a voter is to assign a low likeability score to the politician. But only Americans show a partisan bias even among those with the strongest Moral Identity Internalization.

Moral Identity and Partisan Identity

Our results across two countries show that the Internalization of voters' moral identity and Partisan Identity Centrality matter for how people evaluate politicians involved in moral transgressions. Our models, however, do not estimate these effects simultaneously

Figure 10: Predicted Probabilities of Difference in Likeability of In and Outgroup Politicians for levels of Moral Identity Internalization (England)

primarily because the addition of another interaction level stresses the data we have to the point that we do not have a great deal of confidence in the results. However, as we show in Supplementary Materials Tables A1.17 and A1.18, which enter both partisan and moral identities into the model, the findings described above hold. Both partisan and moral identities help explain voters' evaluations of transgressing politicians.

Beyond these analyses, we acknowledge the possibility that these identities might interact or compete. However, we are unable to test this possibility here. Although we conducted studies with large representative samples, these samples are still not large enough to test the complex interactions involved, and are too skewed on the distribution of moral identity – given that people cannot be randomly assigned to levels of moral (or partisan) identity - to be to confidently explore potential interactions. Further research is needed to address this question.

Discussion and Conclusion

This study examines how voters' heterogeneous responses to politicians' moral violations depend on more than just partisanship, examining how partisan social identity and moral identity both drive responses to such politicians. We find that Partisan Identity Centrality and Moral Identity Internalization both matter for voters' evaluations of politicians involved in moral transgressions. Our findings should encourage other researchers to consider how voters' multiple social identities that depend on degrees of internalization and situational factors are accessed when making moral judgments, including identities beyond those we have studied here. This research expands upon our understanding of partisan effects as identified by Blais et al. (2010) and Walter and Redlawsk (2019, 2021; Redlawsk & Walter, 2024) who used a group affiliation measure of

partisan identification, rather than one focused on social identity (Bankert, et al. 2017). By moving to a social identity perspective on partisanship here, we can better compare its effects to another social identity likely to be relevant to moral transgression, voters' moral identities.

We find that politicians involved in moral violations are perceived as less likeable than politicians involved in social norm violations. In the U.S., Democrats perceive politicians involved in moral violations as less likeable than Republicans. In England, however, we find no partisan difference in the overall likeability of politicians involved in moral violations. Out of the partisans groups examined, U.S. Republicans seem to be most tolerant to moral violations, significant more so than any of the other partisans in the U.S. or England. We find that both in the U.S. and England, voters evaluate politicians engaged in moral violations who belong to their party (ingroup) more positively than politicians who do not (outgroup). However, the ingroup bias is stronger for partisans in the U.S. and Republicans have a stronger ingroup bias than Democrats. Republicans in the US are the least likely to rate their own party's politician as unlikeable. In both countries the ingroup bias is positively related to voters' internalization of their partisan identity, i.e. the higher voters' partisan identity internalization the stronger their ingroup bias in evaluating politicians' immoral behavior. This study thus confirms earlier partisanship findings that did not measure party identification as a social identity, as we do here.

We also find that in both countries voters' moral identities matter for how they evaluate politicians involved in moral transgressions. The more internalized the moral identity the more negatively voters evaluate transgressors. Most of our findings are replicated in both countries. However, ingroup bias in the transgressor's likeability evaluation persists in the U.S. among those with higher moral identity internalization, while

no such effects are found in England. We think that this difference reflects the differential degrees that electorates in these two countries are polarized along partisan lines and hold animosity towards the partisan outgroup. Some studies indicate that the U.S. scores higher on such affective polarization than England (Iyengar, Sood & Lelkes, 2012; Bozell, Gentzkow & Shapiro, 2020). Perhaps, further, moral identity is tied more directly to partisan identity in the U.S. than it is in England. Nevertheless, we are unable to explore this notion further due to the sample size and distribution of moral identity.

A limitation of this study is that people have multiple social identities and we only focus on two of them, namely moral identity and partisan identity. Therefore, this is a simplification of the reality where more social identities such as gender, ethnicity and national identity might compete. In addition, this study examines only people's positive partisan identity; recent work (Bankert, 2020) demonstrates the importance of also examining people's negative partisan identity, as these two partisan identity types tend to have distinct effects. Future work could examine to what extent the bias in voters' moral judgements of transgressing politicians is driven by both voters' positive as well as negative partisan identity. Future work could also examine the consequences of the likeability responses we study here by focusing on electoral outcomes, including vote decisions and likelihood of winning competitive elections.

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Voters' Multiple Identities and Responses to Politicians' Moral Violations

Annemarie S. Walter & David P. Redlawsk

Supplementary Materials

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Appendix 1 Full Models

Figure A1.1 Distribution Dependent Variable Likeability Politician All US Respondents

Note: The mean of this variable Likeability is 2.766 and the standard deviation is .035.

Figure A1.2 Distribution Dependent Variable Likeability Politician All England Respondents

Note: The mean of this variable Likeability is 2.567 and the standard deviation is .031.

Figure A1.3: Distribution Dependent Variable Likeability Politician Partisans US Partisans

Note: The mean of this variable Likeability is 2.786 and the standard deviation is .039.

Figure A1.4: Distribution Dependent Variable Likeability Politician Partisans England Partisans (Labour and Conservative party supporters)

Note: The mean of this variable Likeability is 2.620 and the standard deviation is .043.

Table A1.5: US Study- The Effect of Moral Violation on Likeability of the Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Moral violation	-.250** (.052)
Republican	.171** (.058)
Democrat	-.100 (.057)
Age	-.012** (.001)
Sex	-.165** (.042)
Bachelor education	.019 (.047)
Postgraduate education	.140* (.055)
White	-.026 (.117)
African American	.194 (.129)
Asian	.031 (.044)
Hispanic	-.054 (.133)
Native	.277 (.262)
N	2988
Log-likelihood	4898.780
Cut point 1	-.876
Cut point 2	-.574
Cut point 3	-.298
Cut point 4	.296
Cut point 5	.581
Cut point 6	.904

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Moral Violation exposure to any of the moral violation vignettes (Vignette 1-15) is coded as 1 and exposure to any of the social norm violation vignettes (Vignette 16-18) is coded as 0. The reference category for Partisanship is Nonpartisans. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.*

Table A1.6: US Study- Average Net Marginal Effects of Moral Violation versus Social Violation on the Likeability of Transgressing Politicians

	1 Unlikeable	2	3	4	5	6	7 Likeable
All	.093	.004	-.003	-.016	-.016	-.017	-.035
Democrats	.095	.002	-.005	-.027	-.017	-.016	-.032
Republicans	.090	.007	-.001	-.023	-.016	-.018	-.040
Nonpartisans	.094	.004	-.004	-.027	-.016	-.017	-.033

Note: N=2988

Table A1.7: England Study- The Effect of Moral Violation on the Likeability of Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Moral violation	-1.004** (.052)
Conservative Party supporter	.159* (.069)
Labour Party supporter	.032 (.071)
Liberal Democrat supporter	.124 (.087)
Green Party supporter	-.098 (.110)
UKIP supporter	.201 (.122)
Supporter of another political party	.010 (.186)
Age	-.011* (.001)
Sex	-.044 (.041)
Bachelor education	-.033 (.049)
Postgraduate education	.097 (.069)
White	-.244 (.066)
N	3011
Log-likelihood	-4591.1781
Cut point 1	-1.731
Cut point 2	-1.365
Cut point 3	-1.02
Cut point 4	-.3179
Cut point 5	.105
Cut point 6	.506

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05.*

***significant at .01. For the variable Moral Violation exposure to any of the moral violation vignettes (Vignette 1-15) is coded as 1 and exposure to any of the social norm violation vignettes (Vignette 16-18) is coded as 0. The reference category for Partisanship is Nonpartisans. The reference category for Education is No College Education.*

Table A1.8: England Study- Average Net Marginal Effects of Moral Violation versus Social Violation on the Likeability of Transgressing Politicians

	1 Unlikeable	2	3	4	5	6	7 Likeable
All	.332	.040	.000	-.103	-.089	-.074	-.105
Labour	.328	.042	.003	-.100	-.090	-.074	-.108
Conservative	.315	.048	.010	-.087	-.089	-.078	-.121
Liberal Democrat	.314	.050	.012	-.086	-.089	-.078	-.123
Green	.345	.030	-.010	-.116	-.089	-.069	-.091
UKIP	.298	.058	.021	-.070	-.087	-.082	-.138
Other	.330	.040	.001	-.102	-.089	-.074	-.107
Nonpartisans	.344	.031	-.010	-.115	-.088	-.069	-.092

Note: N=3011

Table A1.9: US Study- The Effects of Shared Partisan Identity on the Likeability of Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	.242 (.057)**
Republican	.325 (.058)**
Age	-.015 (.002)**
Sex	-.227 (.056)**
Bachelor education	-.017 (.063)
Postgraduate education	.217 (.073)**
White	-.093 (.165)
African American	.214 (.177)
Asian	.055 (.203)
Hispanic	-.06 (.185)
Native	.514 (.324)
N	1719
Log-likelihood	-2675.473
Cut point 1	-.460 (.180)
Cut point 2	-.124 (.180)
Cut point 3	.140 (.180)
Cut point 4	.598 (.181)
Cut point 5	.880 (.181)
Cut point 6	1.195 (.183)

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. The reference category for Republican is Democrat. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.*

Table A1.10: England- The Effects of Shared Partisan Identity on the Likeability of Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	.179** (.063)
Conservative Party supporter	.182** (.064)
Age	-.012** (.002)
Sex	-.051 (.061)
Bachelor education	-.055 (.074)
Postgraduate education	.233* (.100)
White	-.298** (.097)
N	1396
Log-likelihood	-2075.796
Cut point 1	-.743 (.120)
Cut point 2	-.371 (.119)
Cut point 3	-.053 (.119)
Cut point 4	.457 (.120)
Cut point 5	.862 (.120)
Cut point 6	1.274 (.129)

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. The reference category for Conservative Party supporter is Labour Party supporter. The reference category for Education is No College Education.*

Table A1.11: US Study- The Effects of Partisan Identity and Partisan Strength on the Likeability of Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	.003 (.105)
Partisan Identity Centrality	
(Moderate)	-.008 (.078)
(Strong)	.075 (.089)
Shared Partisan Identity * Partisan Identity Centrality	
(Shared, Moderate)	.238 (.135)
(Shared, Strong)	.530 (.156)**
Republican	.324 (.058)**
Age	-.015 (.002)**
Sex	-.223 (.056)**
Bachelor education	-.022 (.063)
Postgraduate education	.194 (.073)**
White	-.071 (.165)
African American	.186 (.177)
Asian	.090 (.203)
Hispanic	-.053 (.185)
Native	.502 (.324)
N	1719
Log-likelihood	-2661.647
Cut point 1	-.427 (.188)
Cut point 2	-.091 (.188)
Cut point 3	.173 (.188)
Cut point 4	.638 (.189)
Cut point 5	.927 (.190)
Cut point 6	1.250 (.192)

Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. *significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Partisan Identity Strength the reference category is Weak Partisans. The reference category for Republican is Democrat. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.

Table A1.12: England Study- The Effects of Partisan Identity and Partisan Strength on Moral Principles Likeability of the Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	.039 (.088)
Partisan Identity Centrality	
(Moderate)	-.018 (.079)
(Strong)	.122 (.128)
Shared Partisan Identity * Partisan Identity Centrality	
(Shared, Moderate)	.261 (.137)
(Shared, Strong)	.390 (.211)
Conservative Party supporters	.188** (.065)
Age	-.012** (.002)
Sex	-.047 (.062)
Bachelor education	-.056 (.074)
Postgraduate education	.198* (.101)
White	-.302** (.098)
N	1396
Log-likelihood	-2069.882
Cut point 1	-.715 (.130)
Cut point 2	-.342 (.129)
Cut point 3	-.024 (.129)
Cut point 4	.491 (.130)
Cut point 5	.903 (.133)
Cut point 6	1.324 (.140)

Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parentheses. *significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Partisan Identity Strength the reference category is Weak Partisans. The reference category for Conservative Party supporter is Labour Party supporter. The reference category for Education is No College Education.

Table A1.13: US Study: The Effect of Moral Identity Internalization and Moral Identity Symbolization on Voters' Evaluations on the Likeability of Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Internalization Moral Identity	
(Moderate)	-.187 (.078)*
(Strong)	-.715 (.078)**
Symbolization Moral Identity	
(Moderate)	.091 (.061)
(Strong)	.212 (.083)*
Republican	.284 (.058)**
Age	-.010 (.001)**
Sex	-.150 (.057)**
Bachelor education	-.009 (.063)
Postgraduate education	.199 (.074)
White	-.138 (.166)
African American	.091 (.179)
Asian	-.058 (.204)
Hispanic	-.135 (.186)
Native	.297 (.329)
N	1719
Log-likelihood	-2628.3185
Cut point 1	-.751 (.190)
Cut point 2	-.404 (.189)
Cut point 3	-.128 (.189)
Cut point 4	.349 (.190)
Cut point 5	.643 (.190)
Cut point 6	.970 (.192)

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Internalization Moral Identity the reference category is Weak. For the variable Symbolization Moral Identity the reference category is weak. The reference category for Republican is Democrat. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.*

Table A1.14: England Study: The Effect of Moral Identity Internalization and Moral Identity Symbolization on Voters' Evaluations on the Likeability of Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Internalization Moral Identity (Moderate)	-.234** (.088)
(Strong)	-.694** (.089)
Symbolization Moral Identity (Moderate)	.087 (.065)
(Strong)	.378** (.115)
Conservative Party supporters	.140* (.065)
Age	-.008** (.002)
Sex	.061 (.063)
Bachelor education	-.016 (.075)
Postgraduate education	.242* (.101)
White	-.230* (.098)
N	1396
Log-likelihood	-2038.458
Cut point 1	-.862 (.136)
Cut point 2	-.480 (.135)
Cut point 3	-.153 (.135)
Cut point 4	.377 (.136)
Cut point 5	.805 (.139)
Cut point 6	1.241 (.146)

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Internalization Moral Identity the reference category is Weak. For the variable Symbolization Moral Identity the reference category is weak. The reference category for Republican is Democrat. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.*

Table A1.15: US Study: The Effect of Moral Identity Internalization and Moral Identity Symbolization on Voters' Evaluations on the Likeability of In and Outgroup Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	-.018 (.140)
Internalization Moral Identity	
(Moderate)	-.220 (.096)*
(Strong)	-.828 (.094)**
Shared Partisan Identity*Internalization Moral Identity	
(Shared, Moderate)	.091 (.166)
(Shared, Strong)	.291 (.156)
Symbolization Moral Identity	
(Moderate)	.033 (.074)
(Strong)	.154 (.100)
Shared Partisan Identity* Symbolization Moral Identity	
(Moderate)	.191 (.126)
(Strong)	.236 (.170)
Republican	.285 (.058)**
Age	-.009 (.002)**
Sex	-.153 (.057)**
Bachelor education	-.014 (.064)
Postgraduate education	.197 (.074)**
White	-.151 (.166)
African American	.061 (.179)
Asian	-.075 (.204)
Hispanic	-.146 (.186)
Native	.292 (.329)
N	1719
Log-likelihood	-2613.2437
Cut point 1	-.774 (.195)
Cut point 2	-.423 (.195)
Cut point 3	-.145 (.195)
Cut point 4	.337 (.195)
Cut point 5	.634 (.196)
Cut point 6	.962 (.198)

Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Internalization Moral Identity the reference category is Weak. For the variable Symbolization Moral Identity the reference category is weak. The reference category for Republican is Democrat. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.

Table A1.16: England Study: The Effect of Moral Identity Internalization and Moral Identity Symbolization on Voters' Evaluations on the Likeability of In and Outgroup Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	.080 (.158)
Internalization Moral Identity (Moderate)	-.266* (.107)
(Strong)	-.697** (.107)
Shared Partisan Identity*Internalization Moral Identity (Shared, Moderate)	.088 (.188)
(Shared, Strong)	.016 (.182)
Symbolization Moral Identity (Moderate)	.029 (.079)
(Strong)	.435** (.140)
Shared Partisan Identity* Symbolization Moral Identity (Moderate)	.146 (.137)
(Strong)	-.187 (.236)
Conservative Party Supporters	.146* (.065)
Age	-.009** (.002)
Sex	.058 (.063)
Bachelor education	-.020 (.075)
Postgraduate education	.230* (.101)
White	-.245* (.099)
N	1396
Log-likelihood	-2033.772
Cut point 1	-.862 (.146)
Cut point 2	-.478 (.145)
Cut point 3	-.150 (.145)
Cut point 4	.381 (.146)
Cut point 5	.810 (.1148)
Cut point 6	1.247 (.155)

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. ° significant at .10. For the variable Internalization Moral Identity the reference category is Weak. For the variable Symbolization Moral Identity the reference category is weak. The reference category for Conservative supporter is Labour supporter. The reference category for Education is No College Education.*

Table A1.17: US Study-The Effect of Partisan Identity and Moral Identity Internalization on Voters' Evaluations on the Likeability of In and Outgroup Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	-.190 (.157)
Internalization Moral Identity (Moderate)	-.204(.094)
(Strong)	-.807** (.092)
Shared Partisan Identity*Internalization Moral Identity (Shared, Moderate)	.108 (.165)
(Shared, Strong)	.314* (.155)
Partisan Identity Centrality (Moderate)	-.005 (.078)
(Strong)	.086 (.090)
Shared Partisan Identity* Partisan Identity Centrality (Moderate)	.265 (.136)*
(Strong)	.571 (.156)**
Republican	.287** (.058)
Age	-.010** (.002)
Sex	-.144* (.057)
Bachelor education	-.006 (.064)
Postgraduate education	.202** (.074)
White	-.129 (.167)
African American	.060 (.179)
Asian	-.027 (.205)
Hispanic	-.130 (.186)
Native	.251 (.329)
N	1719
Log-likelihood	-2602.939
Cut point 1	-.782 (.198)
Cut point 2	-.430 (.198)
Cut point 3	-.151 (.198)
Cut point 4	.336 (.198)
Cut point 5	.636 (.199)
Cut point 6	.969 (.201)

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Internalization Moral Identity the reference category is Weak. For the variable Partisan Identity Strength the reference category is weak. The reference category for Republican is Democrat. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.*

Table A1.18: England Study-The Effect of Partisan Identity and Moral Identity Internalization on Voters' Evaluations on the Likeability of In and Outgroup Moral Principles Transgressing Politicians

	Coefficient (Standard error)
Shared Partisan Identity	-.009 (.162)
Internalization Moral Identity	
(Moderate)	-.245* (.107)
(Strong)	-.669** (.106)
Shared Partisan Identity*Internalization Moral Identity	
(Shared, Moderate)	.071 (.186)
(Shared, Strong)	.027 (.180)
Partisan Identity Centrality	
(Moderate)	.004 (.079)
(Strong)	.064 (.129)
Shared Partisan Identity* Partisan Identity Centrality	
(Moderate)	.250 (.138)
(Strong)	.447* (.213)
Conservative Party Supporters	.163** (.065)
Age	-.009** (.002)
Sex	.055 (.063)
Bachelor education	-.018 (.075)
Postgraduate education	.231* (.102)
White	-.258** (.098)
N	1379
Log-likelihood	-2034.598
Cut point 1	-.920 (.148)
Cut point 2	-.535 (.147)
Cut point 3	-.207 (.1147)
Cut point 4	.322 (.148)
Cut point 5	.749 (.150)
Cut point 6	1.186 (.157)

*Note: Model estimated is ordered probit. Standard errors in parantheses. * significant at .05. **significant at .01. For the variable Internalization Moral Identity the reference category is Weak. For the variable Partisan Identity Strength the reference category is weak. The reference category for Republican is Democrat. The reference category for Education is No College Education. The reference category for the variable Race is Mixed/Other.*

Appendix 2 Study Details

Table A2.1: Treatment Groups Vignette Study US

	Moral Foundation Violated	Partisanship Actor
1	Care	Republican
2	Care	Democrat
3	Care	Non-partisan
4	Fairness	Republican
5	Fairness	Democrat
6	Fairness	Non-partisan
7	Loyalty	Republican
8	Loyalty	Democrat
9	Loyalty	Non-partisan
10	Authority	Republican
11	Authority	Democrat
12	Authority	Non-partisan
13	Sanctity	Republican
14	Sanctity	Democrat
15	Sanctity	Non-partisan
16	Social Norm	Republican
17	Social Norm	Democrat
18	Social Norm	Non-partisan

Table A2.2: Treatment Groups Vignette Study England

	Moral Foundation Violated	Partisanship Actor
1	Care	Conservative Party
2	Care	Labour Party
3	Care	Non-partisan
4	Fairness	Conservative Party
5	Fairness	Labour Party
6	Fairness	Non-partisan
7	Loyalty	Conservative Party
8	Loyalty	Labour Party
9	Loyalty	Non-partisan
10	Authority	Conservative Party
11	Authority	Labour Party
12	Authority	Non-partisan
13	Sanctity	Conservative Party
14	Sanctity	Labour Party
15	Sanctity	Non-partisan
16	Social Norm	Conservative Party
17	Social Norm	Labour Party
18	Social Norm	Non-partisan

Table A2.3: US Sample Demographics

Variable	
% Female	52.65
Mean Age (standard deviation)	50.53 (.30)
% White	69.75
% African American	12.42
% Hispanic	8.81
% Asian	5.16
% Native American	.76
% No college degree	49.48
% Bachelor degree	31.54
% Postgraduate degree	18.98
% Democrat	45.27
% Republican	37.85
% Nonpartisan	16.87
% Conservative	32.98
% Moderate	40.96
% Liberal	26.06
% No religion/ Spiritual/ Atheist/ Agnost	27.30
% Christian	63.58
% Jewish	4.14
% Born Again Christian If Christian	57.60
% Attending Religious Services Once a Month or More	32.64

N=2993. For the Variable Born Again Christian N=1967

Table A2.4: England Sample Demographics

Variable	
% Female	55.97
Mean Age (standard deviation)	49.468 (.301)
% White	88.79
% No college degree	67.55
% Bachelor degree	22.59
% Postgraduate degree	9.85
% Labour supporters	29.43
% Conservative supporters	39.55
% Nonpartisan	11.21
% Conservative	36.00
% Moderate	24.35
% Liberal	39.65
% No religion	44.92
% Christian	48.04
% Born Again Christian If Christian	80.18
% Attending Religious Services Once a Month or More	14.37

N=3014. For the Variable Born Again Christian N=1448

Table A2.5: US Study-Randomization Checks

Variable	Chi Square (p.value) at 17 degrees of freedom
Female (0-1)	4.67 (.099)
Age (Anova)	.57 (.916)
White (0-1)	21.359 (.221)
African American (0-1)	16.957 (.457)
Hispanic (0-1)	16.124 (.515)
Asian (0-1)	10.453(.884)
Native (0-1)	17.014 (.453)
Education (0-2) (Anova)	.82 (.6715)
Democrat (0-1)	16.297 (.503)
Republican (0-1)	13.419 (.708)
Nonpartisan (0-1)	13.934 (.672)
Political views (0-4)	1.40 (.128)
Denomination (Anova)	1.15 (.302)

Note: To further assess balance, we estimated a multinomial logistic regression model using the variables in the table to predict treatment assignment. The chi-square from this model 312.50 (.652) indicating that the variables do not jointly predict treatment assignment. N=2993.

Table A2.6: England Study-Randomization Checks

Variable	Chi Square (p.value) at 17 degrees of freedom
Female (0-1)	11.7540 (.814)
Age (Anova)	.80 (.693)
White (0-1)	11.022 (.855)
Education (0-2) (Anova)	0.52 (.945)
Conservative supporters (0-1)	14.707 (.617)
Labour supporters (0-1)	15.690 (.546)
Liberal democrat supports (0-1)	16.211 (.509)
UKIP supporters (0-1)	14.945 (.599)
Green supporters (0-1)	17.281 (.436)
Other supporters (0-1)	13.763 (.684)
Nonpartisan (0-1)	21.557 (.202)
Political views (0-4)	.66 (.842)
Denomination (Anova)	.80 (.699)

Note: To further assess balance, we estimated a multinomial logistic regression model using the variables in the table to predict treatment assignment. The chi-square from this model 208.49 (.700) indicating that the variables do not jointly predict treatment assignment. N=3014

Table A2.7: US Study- Moral Identity (Aquino and Reed 2002) – Internalization Scale

Individual Items							
Items	Labels	Reverse Coded	Mean	Standard deviation	H _i	Z	Double Monotonous
1	It would make me feel good to be a person who has these characteristics.	N	4.1988	.9302	.56282	55.8471	Y
2	Being someone who has these characteristics is an important part of who I am.	N	3.9612	.9527	.49043	48.4943	Y
4	I would be ashamed to be a person who had these characteristics.	Y	4.0949	1.251	.47903	47.1598	N
7	Having these characteristics is not really important to me.	Y	3.8076	1.238	.48578	49.0291	N
10	I strongly desire to have these characteristics.	N	4.0598	.9657	.49373	49.7135	Y
Scale							
H and Z					.50049	78.4586	
Rho					.82643		

Note: N=2993. Response options are recoded as follows 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Somewhat disagree, 3= Neither agree, nor disagree, 4= Somewhat agree, 5= Strongly agree. Y=Yes, N=No. Method: Mokken Scale Analysis (Mokken 1971). The composite additive scale constructed runs between 5-25 and has a mean of 20.12 and a standard deviation of .07.

Table A2.8: England Study- Moral Identity (Aquino and Reed 2002) – Internalization Scale

Individual Items							
Items	Labels	Reverse Coded	Mean	Standard deviation	H _i	Z	Double Monotonous
1	It would make me feel good to be a person who has these characteristics.	N	4.0989		.54273	53.3118	Y
2	Being someone who has these characteristics is an important part of who I am.	N	3.8195		.47442	47.1323	Y
4	I would be ashamed to be a person who had these characteristics.	Y	4.2256		.42565	41.1601	N
7	Having these characteristics is not really important to me.	Y	3.7127		.43182	43.3192	N
10	I strongly desire to have these characteristics.	N	3.8583		.47645	47.6455	Y
Scale							
H and Z					.46763	72.9231	
Rho					.79272		

Note: N=3014. Response options are recoded as follows 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Somewhat disagree, 3= Neither agree, nor disagree, 4= Somewhat agree, 5= Strongly agree. Y=Yes, N=No. Method: Mokken Scale Analysis (Mokken 1971). The composite additive scale runs from 5 to 25 and has a mean of 19.72 and a standard deviation of .07

Table A2.9: US Study- Moral Identity (Aquino and Reed 2002) – Symbolization Scale

Individual Items							
Items	Labels	Reverse Coded	Mean	Standard deviation	H _i	Z	Double Monotonous
3	I often wear clothes that identify me as having these characteristics.	N	2.8674	1.1621	.45858	45.4252	Y
5	The types of things I do in my spare time (e.g., hobbies) clearly identify me as having these characteristics.	N	3.4898	1.0050	.47933	48.7519	Y
6	The kinds of books and magazines that I read identify me as having these characteristics.	N	3.1667	1.0716	.46701	46.3288	Y
8	The fact that I have these characteristics is communicated to others by my membership in certain organizations.	N	3.1323	1.1390	.46322	47.2503	Y
9	I am actively involved in activities that communicate to others that I have these characteristics.	N	3.3632	1.0729	.47310	47.9385	Y
Scale							
H and Z					.46815	74.4595	
Rho					.79409		

Note: N=2993. Response options are recoded as follows 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Somewhat disagree, 3= Neither agree, nor disagree, 4= Somewhat agree, 5= Strongly agree. Y=Yes, N=No. Method: Mokken Scale Analysis (Mokken 1971). The composite additive scale runs between 5 and 25 and has a mean of 16.02 and a standard deviation of .07.

Table A2.10: England Study- Moral Identity (Aquino and Reed 2002) – Symbolization Scale

Individual Items							
Items	Labels	Reverse Coded	Mean	Standard deviation	H _i	Z	Double Monotonous
3	I often wear clothes that identify me as having these characteristics.	N	2.6473		.45153	44.4363	Y
5	The types of things I do in my spare time (e.g., hobbies) clearly identify me as having these characteristics.	N	3.2399		.48044	48.8600	Y
6	The kinds of books and magazines that I read identify me as having these characteristics.	N	2.9536		.48947	49.1462	Y
8	The fact that I have these characteristics is communicated to others by my membership in certain organizations.	N	2.9970		.48614	49.7907	Y
9	I am actively involved in activities that communicate to others that I have these characteristics.	N	3.1357		.47606	48.5903	Y
Scale							
H and Z					.47666	76.0931	
Rho					.80416		

Note: N=3014. Response options are recoded as follows 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Somewhat disagree, 3= Neither agree, nor disagree, 4= Somewhat agree, 5= Strongly agree. Y=Yes, N=No. Method: Mokken Scale Analysis (Mokken 1971). The composite additive scale runs between 5 and 25 and has a mean of 14.97 and a standard deviation of .07.

Table A2.11: US Study- Partisan Identity Scale (Bankert, Huddy & Rosema 2017)

Individual Items							
Items	Labels	Reverse Coded	Mean	Standard Deviation	H _i	Z	Double Monotonous
1	When people criticize this party, it feels like a personal insult	Y	2.4934		.57480	40.2300	Y
2	When I meet someone who supports this party, I feel connected with this person	Y	2.8782		.64407	45.2006	Y
3	When I speak about this party, I refer to it as "my party"	Y	2.5134		.60801	43.0684	Y
4	When people praise this party, it makes me feel good	Y	2.8914		.64029	44.8388	Y
Scale							
H and Z					.61573	61.1195	
Rho					.84383		

Note: N=2053. Question was not asked to nonpartisans. Response options are recoded as follows 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Agree, 4= Strongly Agree, 5=Don't know. Y=Yes, N=No. Method: Mokken Scale Analysis (Mokken 1971).

Table A2.12: England Study- Partisan Identity Scale (Bankert, Huddy & Rosema 2017)

Individual Items							
Items	Labels	Reverse Coded	Mean	Standard Deviation	H _i	Z	Double Monotonous
1	When people criticize this party, it feels like a personal insult	Y	2.1231		.61426	42.3202	Y
2	When I meet someone who supports this party, I feel connected with this person	Y	2.5896		.63926	44.6948	Y
3	When I speak about this party, I refer to it as “my party”	Y	2.0424		.60087	41.7609	Y
4	When people praise this party, it makes me feel good	Y	2.6115		.62477	43.6646	Y
Scale							
H and Z					.61958	60.9236	
Rho					.84006		

Note: N=2144. Question was not asked to nonpartisans. Response options are recoded as follows 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Agree, 4= Strongly Agree, 5=Don't know. Y=Yes, N=No. Method: Mokken Scale Analysis (Mokken 1971).

Appendix 2 References

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- Bankert, A., Huddy, L & Rosema, M. (2017). Measuring Partisanship as a Social Identity in Multi-Party Systems. *Political Behavior*, 39:103–132
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Appendix 3 Stimulus Material

For the stimulus material of England replace Republican with Conservative Party and Democrat with Labour Party.

Vignette 1 Harm/Care, Republican

You see a Republican politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Vignette 2 Harm/Care, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Vignette 3 Harm/Care, Non-partisan

You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Vignette 4 Fairness/Reciprocity, Republican

You see a Republican politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.

Vignette 5 Fairness/Reciprocity, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.

Vignette 6 Fairness/Reciprocity, Non-partisan

You see a politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.

Vignette 7 Ingroup/Loyalty, Republican

You see a Republican politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Vignette 8 Ingroup/Loyalty, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Vignette 9 Ingroup/Loyalty, Non-partisan

You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Vignette 10 Authority/Respect, Republican

You see a Republican politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Vignette 11 Authority/Respect, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Vignette 12 Authority/Respect, Non-partisan

You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Vignette 13 Purity/Sanctity, Republican

You see a Republican politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Vignette 14 Purity/Sanctity, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Vignette 15 Purity/Sanctity, Non-partisan

You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Vignette 16 Social Norms, Republican

You see a Republican politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

Vignette 17 Social Norms, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

Vignette 18 Social Norms, Non-partisan

You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

Appendix 4 Selection of Vignettes and Pre-Tests

We randomly presented respondents with a single vignette out of a set of 18 vignettes chosen based on pre-testing described below. The vignettes differ in violation of moral foundation (Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority, Sanctity) and whether or not partisan labels were used (None, Democrat, or Republican). In addition, a social norm (i.e., non-moral) violation vignette was included as a control stimulus. The inclusion of the control stimulus allows for a comparison between appraisals of scenarios that depict a moral violation and scenarios that depict a social, but not moral, violation.

The vignettes were developed and pre-tested by the authors, selected from an initial set of 30 potential scenarios in which a politician violates one of the five different moral foundations or a social norm (i.e., unconventional behaviour and non-moral violation). The vignettes were tested without partisan labels. These 30 vignettes were developed on the basis of work by Clifford et al. (2015) and Walter and Redlawsk (2019). Clifford et al. (2015) presents a standardized stimulus database of scenarios based on Moral Foundation Theory (MFT) and also uses a social norm violation as a control stimulus. We revised some of the Clifford et al. (2015) scenarios to focus on politics where there were scenarios that can plausibly occur in everyday politics. We initially developed scenarios with U.S. politics in mind. With the help of several British politics experts we then looked at whether the same scenarios were applicable to the context of England. Wording on several scenarios was slightly adapted, for instance Chief of Police became Chief Constable. In some cases a functionally equivalent scenario was tested. For example in the US we tested 'You see a politician violate the oath of office' and in England we tested 'You see a politician refuse the oath of allegiance to the Crown'.

Like Clifford et al. (2015) we made an effort to eliminate any reference to other foundations to increase the likelihood of isolating the influence of a particular moral foundation. In addition, we followed Clifford et al. (2015)'s vignette formulation of "You see..." to encourage respondents to visualize themselves as third party witnesses, thus all the vignettes start with "You see a politician...". The complete lists of vignettes are displayed in Tables A4.2 and A4.6 as pre-tested in the respective countries. The moral foundation Care has three forms of harm, namely emotional harm to a human, physical harm to a human, and physical harm to a non-human animal. We focus solely on emotional harm to a human as the other forms are less likely to occur in everyday politics.

For the U.S. case, the 30 vignettes were pretested between 16 and 18 June 2020 with a sample of 555 respondents from Amazon's Mechanical Turk (MTurk). Table A2.1 displays the pre-test sample Demographics. For England the 30 vignettes were pretested between 6 and 8 September 2020 using the crowdsourcing platform Prolific, with a sample of 551 respondents. Table A2.2 shows the sample demographics for England. We restricted the pretest to respondents residing in England due to differences in party systems in different countries of the UK, restricting our focus on the main five parties competing in England, respectively the Labour Party, the Conservative Party, the Liberal Democratic Party, the Green Party and the UK Independence Party (UKIP). In both surveys each respondent was presented with a random set of twelve of the vignettes such that each vignettes was rated by approximately 220 respondents to ensure stability of average ratings and enable further psychometric analyses.

After exposure to each vignette the respondents were asked (1) to rate how morally wrong the behavior is on a 5-point scale (labeled not at all wrong, not too wrong, somewhat wrong, very wrong, extremely wrong) and (2) state why the behavior was wrong. The respondents were asked to select one response that best described why they thought the behavior was wrong (it violates moral norms of (a) harm or care; (b) fairness or justice; (c) loyalty; (d) respecting authority; (e) purity or (f)

it violates social norms but does not violate a moral norm. Table A4.2 includes the US respondents' ratings for each vignette and Table A4.6 includes the English respondents' ratings for each vignette. After asking these two questions, respondents were asked how understandable the scenario is and how easily they could imagine what happened in the scenario. Both questions provided a 4-point response scale ranging from very easy to very difficult. The last column in each table displays the percentage of respondents that found the scenario very easy or easy to imagine.

The results of both pre-tests show that the vignettes developed to reflect Care and Fairness score the best in terms of correct categorization. The vignettes developed to reflect Sanctity score well in terms of accurate classification, with exception of the vignette 'You see a married politician is having extramarital homosexual relationships'. Somewhat more challenging is the development of Authority vignettes as the percentage of respondents that correctly classifies the vignettes is considerably lower than for the foundations Care, Fairness and Sanctity. Nevertheless, people still classify the formulated vignettes primarily as Authority. The vignettes that we developed to represent Loyalty and Social Norms perform the weakest as they are not always correctly classified. For instance the vignette 'You see a politician refusing to sing the national anthem when others are singing it', was developed as a Loyalty vignette, but is perceived by respondents in both countries as Authority. Overall, we would say that it is very difficult to formulate vignettes that by all respondents are accurately classified, even the best performing vignette is only correctly classified by 87 per cent of the respondents. The Social Norm vignettes are considered by more respondents not at all wrong than the other vignettes. However, the question if it they should as behaviour defying social norms might not be wrong just odd.

The six vignettes actually used in our experimental study are selected out of this pool of 30 vignettes on the basis of the following four criteria: 1) highest accurate categorization of the first mode and for the second mode lowest score possible; 2) highest score in terms of perceived moral wrongness; 3) vignettes that score well in both countries; 4) imaginability of the scenario is high. Selection on the basis of these criteria has led to the following set of vignettes, see Table A4.0. We feel most content with the vignettes selected for the foundations Care, Fairness, Authority and Sanctity.

Table A4.0: Selected Vignettes on Basis Pre-Tests

Vignette Care: You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems									
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>	
71.24	5.75	5.31	4.87	11.06	1.77	2.65	4.25	90.70	US
77.10	4.67	.47	2.80	14.49	.47	.47	4.76	86.45	ENG
Vignette Fairness: You see a politician make sure only supporters get access to jobs									
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>	
6.28	75.78	8.97	6.28	1.35	1.35	0.90	4.24	90.09	US
3.74	85.05	7.01	.93	.47	2.80	1.40	4.54	86.92	ENG
Vignette Loyalty: You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better									
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>	
11.21	5.83	52.47	8.07	2.24	20.18	20.63	2.45	82.43	US
7.87	5.09	55.09	3.24	.46	28.24	17.59	2.40	88.43	ENG
Vignette Authority: You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police/Chief Constable at a disaster									

Care	Fairness	Loyalty	Authority	Sanctity	Social Norms	Not At All Wrong	Wrong (Mean)	Easy	
18.40	8.96	6.60	55.66	2.83	7.55	3.77	3.86	83.02	US
18.94	7.93	5.73	51.54	4.85	11.01	1.76	4.30	85.02	ENG
Vignette Sanctity: You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager									
Care	Fairness	Loyalty	Authority	Sanctity	Social Norms	Not At All Wrong	Wrong (Mean)	Easy	
19.64	3.57	3.57	7.59	63.39	2.23	2.23	4.45	86.92	US
12.78	1.32	.088	3.96	70.93	10.13	3.96	4.58	84.14	ENG
Vignette Social Norm: You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol/Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag									
Care	Fairness	Loyalty	Authority	Sanctity	Social Norms	Not At All Wrong	Wrong (Mean)	Easy	
9.38	3.57	5.80	14.73	8.48	58.04	45.98	1.99	74.32	US
1.39	.00	.46	30.56	2.78	46.81	27.78	2.27	84.26	ENG

Note: Numbers in Table are percentages. The category that scored the highest as to why the behaviour displayed in the vignette is considered wrong, is printed in bold. The variable Easy shows the percentage of respondents that can easily clearly imagine what happens in the vignette. The variable easy combines the response categories very easy and easy to imagine. The variable Not at all wrong indicates the percentage of respondents who considers the behaviour described in the vignette not at all wrong.

Pre-test Vignettes US Respondents

Table A4.1: U.S. Pre-test Sample Demographics

Variable	
Male (in %)	58.74
Age (mean and standard deviation in brackets)	38.82 (.52)
White (in %)	73.51
Education (Bachelors degree or higher in %)	74.05
Democrat (in %)	55.86
Republican in %	33.69
Christian (in %)	54.23
Born Again Christian If Christian (in %)	52.49
Attendance Religious Services Once a Month or More (in %)	28.65

Note: N=555 For the Variable Born Again Christian N =301.

Table A4.2: US Pre-test Respondents Ratings of Vignettes

Scenario	Foundation	Care	Fairness	Loyalty	Authority	Sanctity	Social Norms	Not At All Wrong	Wrong (Mean)	Easy
You see a politician mocking an opponent when the opponent stutters during a debate*	Care	68.30	4.91	4.46	8.48	8.48	5.36	2.68	3.71	88.39
You see a politician say that an opponent is “too stupid to do the job”	Care	51.57	8.52	4.48	11.66	10.31	13.45	9.87	3.04	91.98
You see a politician step back when a severely burned constituent tries to shake hands	Care	59.29	7.52	7.96	7.52	6.64	11.06	3.54	3.35	90.71
You see a politician laugh out loud at a voter who asks for help	Care	62.83	8.41	8.41	6.64	9.29	4.42	4.42	3.80	86.22
You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems	Care	71.24	5.75	5.31	4.87	11.06	1.77	2.65	4.25	90.70
You see a politician make sure only supporters get access to jobs*	Fairness	6.28	75.78	8.97	6.28	1.35	1.35	0.90	4.24	90.09
You see a politician lying about credentials during the campaign	Fairness	4.41	67.40	7.49	7.49	7.49	5.73	2.20	4.14	92.48
You see a politician give a valuable contract to a company run by a family member	Fairness	5.53	69.59	9.68	5.07	4.61	5.53	4.61	3.79	88.94
You see a politician accepting help from foreign countries to win an election	Fairness	3.15	57.66	18.02	9.46	6.31	5.41	1.80	4.18	89.19
You see a politician providing needed help only to voters in the same political party	Fairness	11.82	62.27	14.09	4.09	2.27	5.45	6.36	3.66	94.09
You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better	Loyalty	11.21	5.83	52.47	8.07	2.24	20.18	20.63	2.45	82.43
You see a politician joke about the stupidity of Americans*	Loyalty	27.80	5.83	43.05	9.42	6.73	7.17	5.38	3.49	84.75
You see a politician refusing to sing the national anthem when others are singing it	Loyalty	5.45	4.55	28.18	41.82	4.55	15.45	20.00	2.80	82.19

You see a politician supporting another country's team at the Olympics	Loyalty	7.24	4.52	68.33	5.43	3.17	11.31	19.46	2.68	79.64
You see a politician violate the oath of office	Loyalty	7.52	26.11	23.89	34.96	4.42	3.10	2.21	4.16	88.50
You see a politician refuse to carry out a valid court order	Authority	5.56	35.19	5.09	43.52	6.02	4.63	3.24	3.58	88.43
You see a politician turn away and ignore the party leader*	Authority	10.16	4.81	32.09	41.71	4.81	6.42	15.00	2.67	87.67
You see a politician ignoring Constitutional requirements	Authority	4.11	35.16	5.02	48.86	4.57	2.28	0.91	4.40	89.95
You see a politician hunting where the town has posted no-hunting signs	Authority	10.67	22.67	6.22	49.78	3.56	7.11	3.56	3.90	93.27
You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster	Authority	18.40	8.96	6.60	55.66	2.83	7.55	3.77	3.86	83.02
You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager	Sanctity	19.64	3.57	3.57	7.59	63.39	2.23	2.23	4.45	86.92
You see a politician watching videos of people having sex with animals	Sanctity	5.43	3.17	6.79	5.43	73.76	5.43	0.90	4.11	69.54
You see a politician getting drunk and vomiting at an official event	Sanctity	4.46	3.13	3.13	8.93	64.29	16.07	4.46	3.55	80.80
You see a politician leave the restroom without washing hands	Sanctity	7.76	3.20	5.48	2.74	61.64	19.18	9.59	3.01	90.41
You see a married politician is having extramarital homosexual relationships*	Sanctity	18.75	12.50	27.67	8.48	24.11	8.48	2.64	3.74	91.47
You see a politician wearing a dirty t-shirt and torn jeans at their own inauguration	Social Norms	6.25	5.80	4.91	42.86	22.32	17.86	15.63	2.91	73.66
You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag	Social Norms	9.38	3.57	5.80	14.73	8.48	58.04	45.98	1.99	74.32
You see a politician eating tomato soup with a fork at a restaurant	Social Norms	0.0	2.29	3.67	11.93	8.26	73.85	59.17	1.77	71.88

You see a politician watching a sports event on a cell phone during a meeting	Social Norms	3.64	7.73	12.27	44.55	1.36	30.45	6.82	3.00	88.58
You see a politician celebrate after losing an election	Social Norms	7.27	4.09	18.64	9.09	4.55	56.36	40.00	2.07	60.00

Note: N=555. The category that scored the highest as to why the behaviour displayed in the vignette is considered wrong, is printed in bold. The variable Easy shows the percentage of respondents that can easily clearly imagine what happens in the vignette. The variable easy combines the response categories very easy and easy to imagine. The variable Not at all wrong indicates the percentage of respondents who considers the behaviour described in the vignette not at all wrong. *moral violations vignettes part of study Walter and Redlawsk (2019). ** moral violation vignette part of Clifford et al. 2015.

Pre-test Vignettes England Respondents

Table A4.3: England Pre-test Sample Demographics

Variable	
Male (in %)	38.84
Age (mean and standard deviation in brackets)	33.44 (.51)
White (in %)	72.77
Education (Bachelors degree or higher in %)	48.28
Labour (in %)	43.74
Conservative in %	20.87
Liberal Democrat in %	10.89
UKIP in %	1.63
Green in %	10.34
Conservatives in %	18.87
Moderates in %	30.13
Liberals in %	50.99
No religion (in%)	68.78
Religion(in %)	31.22
Christian (in %)	23.23
Born Again Christian If Christian (in %)	20.47
Attendance Religious Services Once a Month or More	?

Note: N=551 For the Variable Born Again Christian N = 127.

Table A4.4: English Pre-test Respondents Ratings of Vignettes

Scenario	Foundation	Care	Fairness	Loyalty	Authority	Sanctity	Social Norms	Not At All Wrong	Wrong (Mean)	Easy
You see a politician mocking an opponent when the opponent stutters during a debate*	Care	77.06	2.75	1.38	3.21	9.17	6.42	1.83	4.15	91.20
You see a politician say that an opponent is "too stupid to do the job"	Care	62.61	8.11	1.35	9.01	8.56	10.36	4.95	3.28	94.59
You see a politician step back when a severely burned constituent tries to shake hands	Care	74.66	4.98	2.71	6.33	5.88	5.43	2.26	3.94	89.14
You see a politician laugh out loud at a voter who asks for help	Care	73.91	.87	5.22	4.35	9.57	6.09	.43	4.10	84.35
You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems	Care	77.10	4.67	.47	2.80	14.49	.47	.47	4.76	86.45
You see a politician make sure only supporters get access to jobs	Fairness	3.74	85.05	7.01	.93	.47	2.80	1.40	4.54	86.92
You see a politician lying about credentials during the campaign	Fairness	.99	69.46	13.30	6.40	1.48	8.37	.49	4.49	92.61
You see a politician give a valuable contract to a company run by a family member	Fairness	.44	81.94	5.29	3.52	1.32	7.49	4.85	3.96	90.67
You see a politician accepting help from foreign countries to win an election	Fairness	.92	74.19	11.06	3.69	2.30	7.83	1.38	4.22	89.86
You see a politician providing needed help only to voters in the same political party	Fairness	12.44	62.67	8.89	1.33	2.67	12.00	2.67	3.82	90.18
You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better**	Loyalty	7.87	5.09	55.09	3.24	.46	28.24	17.59	2.40	88.43
You see a politician joke about the stupidity of the British people	Loyalty	32.29	2.24	37.22	8.52	9.42	10.31	2.69	3.80	91.48

You see a politician refusing to sing the national anthem when others are singing it	Loyalty	.45	.00	19.64	66.07	1.34	12.50	15.63	2.78	88.34
You see a politician supporting another country's team at the Olympics	Loyalty	.00	.00	57.67	7.91	.00	34.42	30.70	2.18	83.26
You see a politician refuse the oath of allegiance to the Crown.	Loyalty	.45	.45	16.36	71.36	2.73	8.64	15.45	3.27	78.08
You see a politician refuse to carry out a valid court order	Authority	1.36	43.64	5.45	43.64	.91	5.00	.91	4.25	77.27
You see a politician turn away and ignore the party leader	Authority	7.48	.47	31.78	45.79	1.87	12.62	8.88	2.76	86.45
You see a politician ignoring Constitutional precedents	Authority	2.17	18.26	9.57	58.26	1.47	10.00	1.74	3.84	71.18
You see a politician participate in an illegal fox hunt	Authority	43.75	12.05	2.68	13.48	20.09	7.59	.45	4.41	90.18
You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief Constable at a disaster	Authority	18.94	7.93	5.73	51.54	4.85	11.01	1.76	4.30	85.02
You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager	Sanctity	12.78	1.32	.088	3.96	70.93	10.13	3.96	4.58	84.14
You see a politician watching videos of people having sex with animals	Sanctity	6.94	.93	.00	.93	87.04	4.17	.46	4.61	66.67
You see a politician getting drunk and vomiting at an official event	Sanctity	.00	.00	.92	25.69	54.13	19.27	2.75	3.55	91.28
You see a politician leave the restroom without washing hands	Sanctity	5.80	.89	.89	3.13	51.79	37.50	8.04	3.30	93.75
You see a married politician is having extramarital homosexual relationships*	Sanctity	34.11	14.95	30.84	4.21	5.61	10.28	10.75	3.67	87.24
You see a politician wearing a dirty t-shirt and torn jeans at their own election night count	Social Norms	.45	1.80	1.80	44.59	4.50	48.20	17.12	2.59	80.09
You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag	Social Norms	1.39	.00	.46	30.56	2.78	46.81	27.78	2.27	84.26

You see a politician eating tomato soup with a fork at a restaurant		.44	.00	.44	5.33	3.11	90.67	48.00	2.03	67.56
You see a politician watching a sports event on a mobile phone during a meeting	Social Norms	1.36	3.62	6.79	53.85	.45	33.94	1.81	3.52	90.05
You see a politician celebrate after losing an election	Social Norms	.89	5.33	37.78	11.56	3.11	41.33	21.33	2.63	68.89

Note: N=557. The category that scored the highest as to why the behaviour displayed in the vignette is considered wrong, is printed in bold. The variable Easy shows the percentage of respondents that can easily clearly imagine what happens in the vignette. The variable easy combines the response categories very easy and easy to imagine. The variable Not at all wrong indicates the percentage of respondents who considers the behaviour described in the vignette not at all wrong. *moral violations vignette part of study Walter and Redlawsk 2019. ** moral violation vignette part of Clifford et al. 2015.

Appendix 5: Questionnaire

England

Note: United States survey is the same except for the replacement of the parties listed with Democrats and Republicans, Education options are U.S. based, Race and ethnicity use U.S. based options, location is identified by State instead of region, income is recorded in dollars, the vignettes are adjusted to use English references such as Constable instead of Police, and House of Commons instead of Congress, and revisions to spelling to match U.S. spelling. The full U.S. survey is available upon request to the authors.

Q1 This is a study about how people respond to information about politicians, and your participation in the study is voluntary. If you decide to participate, you will answer questions about how you would feel if a politician exhibited certain behaviors. You will also be asked to provide some demographic information, such as your age and gender. You must be at least 18 years old and a resident in England to participate in this study. The study should take approximately 15 minutes, and needs to be completed in a single session (without taking breaks). Participation in this study is voluntary. You may choose not to participate, and you may choose not to answer any questions with which you are not comfortable. You may also withdraw at any time during the study procedures, but unless you participate in the study until the end you will not receive payment for participation.

The research team and the Institutional Review Board (a committee that reviews research studies in order to safeguard the welfare of research participants) at the University of Delaware are the only parties that will be allowed to see the data, except as required by law. If a report of this study is published, or the results are presented at a professional conference, only group results will be stated—the identity of individual participants will not be disclosed. All study data will be kept for at least three years.

There are only minimal risks associated with this study. You may be exposed to information about political policies or positions that you dislike or are uncomfortable with. You will receive payment for your time as specified by Dynata. You may also receive an indirect benefit by learning more about the thoughts and feelings you have in response to political candidates. Finally, there may be a general societal benefit in that we will learn more about responses to candidates and communications during political campaigns.

Do you wish to continue? Clicking "YES" will indicate your consent to use your responses in our study.

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Q2 First, we will ask some questions about you that will help us categorize your responses. What is the highest educational or work-related qualification you have? Please choose from the dropdown list.

▼ No formal qualifications (1) ... Prefer not to say (25)

Q3 What is your age?

▼ 18 (18) ... 100+ (100)

Q4 What is your gender?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Nonbinary (3)
- Other, please specify (4) _____

Q5 To which ONE of these groups do you consider you belong? Please select from the dropdown list.

▼ White British (1) ... Refused (21)

Q6 Do you regard yourself as belonging to any particular religion, and if so, to which of these do you belong?

▼ No, I do not regard myself as belonging to any particular religion. (1) ... Prefer not to say (34)

IF CHRISTIAN OF ANY TYPE:

Q7 Would you call yourself a born-again Christian, that is, have you personally had a conversion experience related to Jesus Christ?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Q8 How often do you attend religious services, apart from social obligations such as weddings or funerals?

- Never (1)

- Once a year or less (2)
- A few times a year (3)
- Once or twice a month (4)
- Almost every week (5)
- Every week or more than once a week (6)

Q8A What is your gross household income?

Gross HOUSEHOLD income is the combined income of all those earners in a household from all sources, including wages, salaries, or rents, and before tax deductions.

▼ Less than £10,000 (1) ... Don't Know (16)

Q8B Which area of the UK do you live in?

▼ North East (1) ... Other/Non UK (13)

Q10-Q44 Next, we would like to have you consider an action of a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

RANDOM SELECTION OF ONE OF THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS Q10-Q44

You see a Conservative politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

You see a Labour politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

You see a Conservative politician making sure only supporters get access to jobs.

You see a Labour politician making sure only supporters get access to jobs.

You see a politician making sure only supporters get access to jobs.

You see a Conservative politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

You see a Labour politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

You see a Conservative politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief Constable at a disaster.

You see a Labour politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief Constable at a disaster.

You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief Constable at a disaster.

You see a Conservative politician was found having sex with a teenager.

You see a Labour politician was found having sex with a teenager.

You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.

You see a Conservative politician carrying briefing papers to the Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag.

You see a Labour politician carrying briefing papers to the Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag.

You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag.

END RANDOM SELECTION

Q45 When you think about this politician's behaviour, how does it make you **feel about the politician?**

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Not at all (1)	Slightly (2)	Moderately (3)	Quite a bit (4)	Extremely (5)
Anxious	☐				
Optimistic about humanity	☐				
Contemptuous	☐				
Warm-hearted	☐				
Hopeful	☐				
Enthusiastic	☐				
Ashamed	☐				
Guilty	☐				
Admiration	☐				
Compassion	☐				
Proud	☐				
Disgusted	☐				
Uplifted	☐				
Angry	☐				

Q47 How would you rate the politician in the scenario on the following characteristics? Click the bubble that represents where you would place this politician on each one.

RANDOMIZE ORDER	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Immoral	☐	Moral						
Incompetent	☐	Competent						
Unfit for office	☐	Fit for office						
Unsympathetic	☐	Sympathetic						
Unlikeable	☐	Likeable						
Dishonest	☐	Honest						
Weak leader	☐	Strong leader						
Untrustworthy	☐	Trustworthy						
Uncompassionate	☐	Compassionate						
Uninspiring	☐	Inspiring						

Q48 How likely is it that you would vote for this politician?

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
0 - Not at all likely	☐	10 - Extremely likely										

Q49 When you think about this politician's behaviour, to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Not at all (1)	Slightly (2)	Moderately (3)	Quite a bit (4)	Extremely (5)
The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behaviour	☐				
The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behaviour	☐				
The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behaviour	☐				
The politician should receive a warning for his/her behaviour from the party leader	☐				
This politician should because of his/her behaviour be reported to authorities	☐				
I would share a post about this politician's behaviour with my social network online	☐				
The politician should be forgiven for his/ her behaviour	☐				
I would report the politician for his/her behaviour to authorities	☐				
The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behaviour	☐				

Q51 Thinking about the behaviour of the politician, how wrong is it?

- Not at all wrong (1)
- Not too wrong (2)
- Somewhat wrong (3)
- Very wrong (4)
- Extremely wrong (5)

Q50 What was the politician's party as described in the scenario?

- Conservative Party (1)
- Labour Party (2)
- No Party Listed (3)
- Do not know (4)

Q53 Now, we have some more questions for purposes of categorizing your responses to the previous questions. As a reminder, your individual responses will not be shared with anyone outside of the research team.

In general, how interested are you in politics and public affairs?

- Very interested (1)
- Somewhat interested (2)
- Slightly interested (3)
- Not at all interested (4)

Q54 How often do you pay attention to what's going on in government and politics?

- Always (1)
- Most of the time (2)
- About half the time (3)
- Some of the time (4)
- Never (5)

Q55 In general, how would you describe your political views?

- Very conservative (1)
- Conservative (2)
- Moderate (3)
- Liberal (4)
- Very liberal (5)

Q56 Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or what?

- Conservative (1)
- Labour (2)
- Liberal Democrat (3)
- United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP) (4)
- Green (5)
- Other party, please specify (6) _____
- None (7)
- Do not know (9)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = None Or Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Do not know

Q59 Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If yes, which party?

- Conservative (1)
- Labour (2)
- Liberal Democrat (3)
- United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP) (4)
- Green (5)
- Other, please specify (6) _____
- No – None (7)
- Don't know (9)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Conservative Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Conservative

Q57 Would you call yourself a very strong, fairly strong, or not very strong Conservative Party supporter?

- Very strong (1)
 - Fairly strong (2)
 - Not very strong (3)
 - Don't know (9)
-

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Labour Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Labour

Q58 Would you call yourself a very strong, fairly strong, or not very strong Labour Party supporter?

- Very strong (1)
- Fairly strong (2)
- Not very strong (3)
- Don't know (9)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Liberal Democrat Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Liberal Democrat

Q58A Would you call yourself a very strong, fairly strong, or not very strong Liberal Democratic Party supporter?

- Very strong (1)
- Fairly strong (2)
- Not very strong (3)
- Don't know (9)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP) Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)

Q58B Would you call yourself a very strong, fairly strong, or not very strong UKIP supporter?

- Very strong (1)
- Fairly strong (2)
- Not very strong (3)
- Don't know (9)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Green Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Green

Q58C Would you call yourself a very strong, fairly strong, or not very strong Green Party supporter?

- Very strong (1)
- Fairly strong (2)
- Not very strong (3)
- Don't know (9)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or what? Other party, please specify Is Not Empty Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... Other, please specify Is Not Empty

Q58D Would you call yourself very strong, fairly strong, or not very strong $\{Q56/ChoiceTextEntryValue/6\}\{Q59/ChoiceTextEntryValue/8\}$ supporter?

- Very strong (1)
- Fairly strong (2)
- Not very strong (3)
- Don't know (9)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Conservative Or Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Labour Or Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Liberal Democrat Or Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = United Kingdom

Independence Party (UKIP) Or Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or... = Green

Q61 You said that you think of yourself as a {Q56/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} supporter. Thinking about this party, how much do you agree with these statements?

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Disagree (3)	Strongly disagree (4)	Don't know (5)
When people criticize this party, it feels like a personal insult.	☐				
When I meet someone who supports this party, I feel connected with this person.	☐				
When I speak about this party, I refer to it as "my party."	☐				
When people praise this party, it makes me feel good.	☐				

Display This Question:

If Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Conservative Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Labour Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Liberal Democrat Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to

one of the parties than the others? If y... = United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP) Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... = Green

Q62 You said that you feel a little closer toward the {Q59/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices} Party. Thinking about this party, how much do you agree with these statements?

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Strongly agree (1)	Agree (2)	Disagree (3)	Strongly disagree (4)	Don't know (5)
When people criticize this party, it feels like a personal insult.	☐				
When I meet someone who supports this party, I feel connected with this person.	☐				
When I speak about this party, I refer to it as "my party."	☐				
When people praise this party, it makes me feel good.	☐				

Display This Question:
 If Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Conservative, Labour, Liberal Democrat or what? Other party, please specify Is Not Empty Or Or Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If y... Other, please specify Is Not Empty

Q63 You said that you feel a little closer toward the {Q56/ChoiceTextEntryValue/6}{Q59/ChoiceTextEntryValue/8}. Thinking about this party, how much do you agree with these statements?

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Strongly agree (1)	Agree (2)	Disagree (3)	Strongly disagree (4)	Don't know (5)
When people criticize this party, it feels like a personal insult.	☐				
When I meet someone who supports this party, I feel connected with this person.	☐				
When I speak about this party, I refer to it as "my party."	☐				
When people praise this party, it makes me feel good.	☐				

Q64 How likely is it that you would ever vote for each of the following parties?

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Very unlikely 0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Very likely 10
Conservative Party	☐										
Labour Party	☐										
Liberal Democratic Party	☐										
Green Party	☐										
United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)	☐										

Q116 Thinking back again to the scenario you read earlier about a politician's behaviour, what was the politician's party as described in the scenario?

- Conservative Party (1)
- Labour Party (2)
- No Party Listed (3)
- Do not know (4)

Q65 When you decide whether something is right or wrong, to what extent are the following considerations relevant to your thinking? Please rate each statement using the following scale, from not at all relevant to extremely relevant.

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Not at all relevant (Has nothing to do with my judgements of right & wrong) (1)	Not very relevant (2)	Slightly relevant (3)	Somewhat relevant (4)	Very relevant (5)	Extremely relevant (One of the most important factors when I judge right and wrong) (6)
Whether or not someone suffered emotionally	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Whether or not some people were treated differently than others	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Whether or not someone's action showed love for his or her country	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Whether or not someone showed a lack of respect for authority	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Whether or not someone violated standards of purity and decency	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Whether or not someone was good at math	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Whether or not someone cared for someone weak or vulnerable	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Whether or not someone acted unfairly	☐					
Whether or not someone did something to betray his or her group	☐					
Whether or not someone conformed to the traditions of society	☐					
Whether or not someone did something disgusting	☐					
Whether or not someone was cruel	☐					
Whether or not someone was denied his or her rights	☐					
Whether or not someone showed a lack of loyalty	☐					
Whether or not an action caused chaos or disorder	☐					
Whether or not someone acted in a way that God would approve of	☐					

Q66 Please read the following sentences and indicate how much you agree or disagree with each.

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Strongly agree (1)	Agree (2)	Some what agree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat disagree (5)	Disagree (6)	Strongly disagree (7)
Compassion for those who are suffering is the most crucial virtue.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
When the government makes laws, the number one principle should be ensuring that everyone is treated fairly.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I am proud of my country's history.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Respect for authority is something all children need to learn.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
People should not do things that are disgusting, even if no one is harmed.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It is better to do good than to do bad.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
One of the worst things a person could do is hurt a defenseless animal.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Justice is the most important requirement for a society.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
People should be loyal to their family members, even when they have done something wrong.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Men and women each have different roles to play in society.

I would call some acts wrong on the grounds that they are unnatural.

It can never be right to kill a human being.

I think it's morally wrong that rich children inherit a lot of money while poor children inherit nothing.

It is more important to be a team player than to express oneself.

If I were a soldier and disagreed with my commanding officer's orders, I would obey anyway because that is my duty.

Chastity is an important and valuable virtue.

People who are successful in business have a right to enjoy their wealth as they see fit.

Society works best when it lets individuals take responsibility for their own lives without telling them what to do.

The government should do more to advance the common good, even if that means limiting the freedom and choices of individuals.

Property owners should be allowed to develop their land or build their homes in any way they choose, as long as they don't endanger their neighbors.

Whether or not everyone was free to do as they wanted.

I think everyone should be free to do as they choose, so long as they don't infringe upon the equal freedom of others.

People should be free to decide what group norms or traditions they themselves want to follow.

Q68 Listed below are some characteristics that might describe a person:

Caring, Compassionate, Fair, Friendly, Generous, Helpful, Hardworking, Honest, and Kind.

The person with these characteristics could be you or it could be someone else.

For a moment, visualize in your mind the kind of person who has these characteristics. Imagine how that person would think, feel, and act.

Q69 Now that you have a clear image of what this person would be like, please indicate how much you disagree or agree with each of the following questions.

RANDOMIZE ORDER	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
It would make me feel good to be a person who has these characteristics.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Being someone who has these characteristics is an important part of who I am.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I often wear clothes that identify me as having these characteristics.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I would be ashamed to be a person who had these characteristics.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The types of things I do in my spare time (e.g., hobbies) clearly identify me as having these characteristics.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The kinds of books and magazines that I read identify me as having these characteristics.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Having these characteristics is not really important to me.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The fact that I have these characteristics is communicated to others by my membership in certain organizations.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I am actively involved in activities that communicate to others that I have these characteristics.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I strongly desire to have these characteristics.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Q75 Finally, we have just a couple more questions before you're done. Thank you for your careful attention to this survey.

how often do you spend time in private religious activities, such as prayer, meditation or study of Scripture?

- Never (1)
- Once a year or less (2)
- A few times a year (3)
- Once or twice a month (4)
- Almost every week (5)
- Every week (6)
- Two or more times per week (7)
- Daily (8)
- More than once a day (9)

Q76 Which, if any, of the following do you believe in?

	Yes (1)	No (2)	Unsure (3)
Heaven (1)	☐	☐	☐
Hell (2)	☐	☐	☐
God (3)	☐	☐	☐

Q77 Following are several statements about religious belief or experience. Please mark the extent to which each statement is true or not true for you.

	Definitely not true (1)	Tends not to be true (2)	Unsure (3)	Tends to be true (4)	Definitely true to me (5)
In my life, I experience the presence of the Divine (i.e., God)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
My religious beliefs are what really lie behind my whole approach to life.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I try hard to carry my religion over into all other dealings in life	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I am religious mostly because it is a source of comfort to me	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I go to my place of worship mostly because I enjoy seeing people I know there	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Q78 Following are a set of moral values that people may or may not find important in their lives.

How do you think the average **Labour supporter** ranks the importance of these values from most important (1) to least important (5)?

Please rank the five values below as you think the average **Labour supporter** would. You must give each value a different rank.

- _____ Authority (respect for authority and tradition) (1)
- _____ Fairness or Justice (commitment to maintaining equality) (2)
- _____ Harm or Care (dislike for the suffering of others) (3)
- _____ Loyalty (commitment to one's own group) (4)
- _____ Purity (maintaining morality or cleanliness) (5)

Q79

Following are a set of moral values that people may or may not find important in their lives.

How do you think the average **Conservative supporter** ranks the importance of these values from most important (1) to least important (5)?

Please rank the five values below as you think the average **Conservative supporter** would. You must give each value a different rank.

- _____ Authority (respect for authority and tradition) (1)
- _____ Fairness or Justice (commitment to maintaining equality) (2)
- _____ Harm or Care (dislike for the suffering of others) (3)
- _____ Loyalty (commitment to one's own group) (4)
- _____ Purity (maintaining morality or cleanliness) (5)